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**Dynamic phenomena
in atmospheric pressure discharges**

Ph.D. Dissertation

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Abstract

This work deals with experimental study on two atmospheric pressure plasma discharges – radiofrequency plasma jet and alternating current gliding arc. Both discharges were investigated primarily in noble gases; namely in helium, neon, argon and krypton. Dynamics of constricted plasma filament(s) was investigated mainly by means of optical methods, especially by high speed camera imaging.

Plasma jet was analyzed within power/gas flow phase space. Three diverse dynamic modes of plasma filament(s) were observed; two self-organized and one chaotic. Striations of plasma string and miscellaneous 3D spatio-temporal plasma structures were observed in the latter mode. Gliding arc was investigated under varying gravity, which was artificially increased using centrifuge (up to 18 g). At higher gravity levels, increased buoyancy force effected strongly the movement of the discharge channel, especially gliding frequency.

Abstrakt

Cílem práce je popsat dynamické projevy plazmatu dvou typů výbojů za atmosférického tlaku – studené radiofrekvenční plazmové trysky a klouzavého výboje typu gliding arc. Tyto výboje jsou studovány především ve vzácných plynech; a to v heliu, neonu, argonu a kryptonu. Dynamika kontrahovaných filamentů plazmatu je zkoumána především pomocí optických metod, zejména rychlé digitální fotografie.

Chování plazmatické trysky bylo probádáno ve fázovém prostoru proměnných výkonu a proudu plynu. Byly pozorovány tři různé dynamické módy vláken kontrahovaného plazmatu; z nich byly dva self-organizované a jeden chaotický. V chaotickém módu byly pozorovány striace plazmatu a rozličné struktury uspořádání plazmatu v prostoru a čase. V případě klouzavého výboje bylo chování plazmatu studováno i za uměle zvýšené gravitace (až 18 g), které bylo dosaženo pomocí centrifugy. Nárůst vztahové síly za zvýšené gravitace silně ovlivnilo pohyb výbojového kanálu, zejména frekvenci jeho klouzání.

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Declaration

I declare that the thesis "Dynamic Phenomena in Atmospheric Pressure Discharges" and the work presented in it are my own. I confirm that:

- where I have consulted the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed;
- where I have quoted from the work of others, the source is always given;
- I have acknowledged all main sources of help.

Brno 12th November 2015

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Jiří Šperka

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Chapter 1

Introduction

People are called creative or crazy when they see a likeness between things that were thought not to be alike before. Creativity, however, entails more than seeing a likeness or drawing a metaphor. Abstracting something new is what matters.

J. A. Scott Kelso [1]

There is no doubt that ionized gas fulfilling requirements to be marked as plasma is fascinating and beautiful matter. During nights, humans always received and admired photons originating from space astrophysical plasmas. Let's briefly mention several examples to demonstrate enormous importance of plasma in almost everything as well: It is believed that up to a few milliseconds after the Big Bang, known as the Quark epoch, the Universe was in a quark–gluon plasma state [2]. Some abiogenesis theories of life's origin on early Earth work with lightning and they were tested by assistance of laboratory electrical discharge, for example, in famous Miller–Urey experiment [3, 4]. No matter, how advanced our current technology is, existence of our civilization still depends on plasma sphere in the centre of our Solar system. I would be not able to write this text on laptop without current plasma-based technology. We are searching for new energy sources and controlled thermonuclear fusion, which is of great interest for many plasma physicists, could be the solution.

Plasmas in laboratories, small-dimensional relatives of astrophysical plasmas, are no less beautiful and complex than plasmas in space – which is connected to plasma scaling [5]. Similarity laws can be applied for different types of laboratory and astrophysical discharges. In this thesis, two distinct laboratory atmospheric pressure discharges are under experimental investigation. Goal of this work is to demonstrate, how does depend dynamic plasma behaviour on experimental parameters and to show that even if the radiofrequency plasma jet and the gliding arc plasma differ not only in their length scale, many dynamic phenomena are related. The fact, that both investigated plasma sources are operated at atmospheric pressure (pressure in gliding arc discharge chamber periodically fluctuates, as will be described later, but we can ignore it in zeroth-order of approximation) is of great importance for this study. Because of this, significant temperature & density gradients, gas flow & buoyancy effects and fast quenching of ionized & excited species can be observed and compared for both plasma sources. The two discharges were studied in the same noble gases (He, Ne, Ar, Kr) to obtain comparable results.

Work in this thesis is divided into two research lines. In the first research line, it focuses

on microscopic¹ high-frequency dynamics of plasma jet constricted filament(s) striations and mesoscopic² self-organization of plasma filaments. In the second research line, the gliding arc discharge with focus on macroscopic³ low-frequency dynamics of plasma string is investigated; this part is multidisciplinary because it combines different disciplines – plasma physics, materials science and hypergravity research. Two main research lines are separated within the text with the exception of theoretical part dealing with atmospheric pressure plasmas and final conclusion in chapter 7, where obtained results are compared. In theoretical part, general introduction to plasma physics is skipped, as it can be found in any plasma physics textbook, e.g. in [6–9]. It is out of scope of this work to describe all aspects of common plasma dynamics because it covers enormous amount of phenomena as can be found e.g. in book [10] “Introduction to plasma dynamics”. This thesis tries to summarize the most interesting and novel findings that arose during experimental work. In spite of the fact that the gliding arc and the radiofrequency plasma jet are the focus of this work, the methods presented in this work can be extended to study other discharges such as microwave plasma torches, stable arc discharges or spark discharges.

Parts of this thesis have been already published in form of scientific journal papers [11–17]. List of publications including submitted papers can be found in section 8.2.

¹Microscopic due to the fact, that the striations of plasma filament(s) in described system (plasma jet) are not to be seen by the unaided human eye because of their very short duration ~ 1 ms and small dimensions ~ 100 μm .

²Mesoscopic due to the fact, that effects of self-organization of filaments in studied system (plasma jet) occur at intermediate time ~ 100 ms and length ~ 1 mm scale. Some regimes of self-organization can be seen by the unaided human eye, but multiple-filaments high-frequency regimes are not possible to be distinguished by unaided eye. In any case, special equipment is needed for exact study of these phenomena.

³Macroscopic due to the fact, that this thesis focuses on study of gliding arc plasma discharge channel on length scales of ~ 1 cm. Time scales of gliding arc depends on the process – lifetime of one individual plasma channel is connected to alternating power supply frequency (~ 10 ms in this work), one gliding arc life cycle lasts for different time periods depending on several discharge parameters, as is described later, but typical time scales are of $\sim 0.1 - 1$ s for this work. Very interesting phenomena can be found also on smaller time and length scales (e.g. structuring of plasma channel with well noticeable cathode and anode layers or electrode erosion) and some of these aspects are briefly mentioned, but not systematically studied in this work.

Chapter 2

Theory

Nature uses only the longest threads to weave her patterns, so each small piece of her fabric reveals the organization of the entire tapestry.

Richard Feynman [18]

2.1 Atmospheric pressure low-temperature plasmas

Atmospheric pressure (AP) discharges¹ in laboratory can be classified as electrical discharges operating at pressure near to standard atmosphere ($1 \text{ atm} \approx 1.013 \times 10^5 \text{ Pa}$). In this section basic aspects of steady state AP plasmas are summarized; mechanisms of AP discharge breakdown are out of scope of this work, but can be found eg. in [20–22]. The AP discharges can be sustained in various gases or their mixtures; employment of ambient air is common due to financial expenses. The length-scale on which AP discharges can be ignited depends usually on breakdown voltage according to Paschen’s law. Atmospheric pressure conditions are sometimes required, e.g. for biomedical applications [23]. Quite impressive example of AP low-temperature discharge is common electric spark. This discharge (an example of AP non-steady state plasma) was macroscopically observed for millennia and was very probably also noticed by ancient Greek philosophers [24,25]. Nowadays AP discharges have many applications, as can be found e.g. in review [26]. For instance continuous AP arc discharge, which was independently discovered by V. Petrov and H. Davy [27], serves as first artificial light source since 19th century. Steady state arc plasmas are example of local thermodynamic equilibrium (LTE) plasma². In the LTE state the mean electron temperature T_e and the mean translation (gas) temperature of heavy species (ions, atoms, molecules, dust particles) T_h are nearly the same. For many utilizations LTE plasmas are not applicable due to high temperature of heavy species T_h , which can lead to damage of temperature sensitive materials. For low-temperature applications employment of non-local thermodynamic equilibrium (non-LTE) plasma³ with substantially lower temperature of heavy species T_h than electrons can be the right choice. Main differences between LTE and non-LTE plasmas can be found in table 2.1.

¹Please note that collocation “atmospheric discharges” can also refer to discharges in planetary atmosphere of Earth or another planet [19].

²LTE plasma is often labeled as thermal plasma.

³Non-LTE plasma is often labeled as non-equilibrium or cold plasma.

Table 2.1: LTE and non-LTE plasmas main characteristics

	LTE plasmas	Non-LTE plasmas
Typical electron density n_e	$T_e = T_h$ $10^{21} - 10^{26} \text{ m}^{-3}$ [26]	$T_e \gg T_h$ $< 10^{19} \text{ m}^{-3}$ [26]
Example	Welding arc [28] $T_e = T_h \approx 1.3 \text{ eV}$ $n_e \approx 1.6 \times 10^{23} \text{ m}^{-3}$	Low-pressure CCP discharge [29] $T_e \approx 1.5 \text{ eV}$ $T_h \approx 300 \text{ K}$ $n_e \approx 10^{16} \text{ m}^{-3}$

In plasmas that are produced by accelerating charged species by electric field, the energy transfer proceeds from electrons with high electrical mobility to heavy neutral particles through inelastic collisions (ionization, excitation, dissociation of molecules), which create plasma reactive species, and elastic collisions, which heat the heavy particles and thus reduce $\langle T_e \rangle$. In atomic gases for electron temperatures below 3 eV the electron energy transfer to the heavy neutral particles is dominated by elastic collisions. In molecular gases for $T_e < 3 \text{ eV}$ the vibrational excitation is either dominant or not negligible [30]. For steady state large-volume discharges the inequality of electron temperature T_e and heavy neutral gas temperature T_g , which can occur due to different mass of electrons and neutral particles, can be expressed by equation for atomic gases that is connected to the investigations of thermal arcs [31]:

$$\frac{T_e - T_g}{T_e} = \frac{m_g}{4 m_e} \left(\frac{\lambda_e e E}{\frac{3}{2} k_B T_e} \right)^2, \quad (2.1)$$

where m_e is the electron mass, m_g the mass of heavy neutral particle, k_B the Boltzmann constant, E the electric field strength, e the elementary charge and λ_e the mean free path of electrons. The term $\lambda_e e E$ is the amount of energy that electron picks up along free path in electric field direction and $\frac{3}{2} k_B T_e$ is the average thermal energy of one electron. Electron-neutral collisions cause continual exchange of energy with a tendency to equilibrate temperatures. Due to validity of following chain $\uparrow p \rightarrow \downarrow \lambda_e \rightarrow \downarrow (T_e - T_g)$ (both T_e and λ_e depend on pressure, but the relative change in T_e with pressure is much smaller than the change in λ_e with pressure, so it doesn't change the result [30]), it is more complicated to maintain non-equilibrium conditions at elevated pressure with high collision rates and short mean free paths [32].

For plasma at steady state under assumption that the power transferred to heavy gas via collisions is lost through thermal conduction only, following relationship can be derived [33]:

$$n_e D^2 \propto \frac{T_g^{3/2}}{p \varepsilon(T_e) K_e(T_e)}, \quad (2.2)$$

where D is the characteristic dimension of plasma, p is the pressure, n_e is the electron density, K_e is the collision rate between electron and neutral particles, ε is an average energy exchanged during each such collision. K_e and ε are function of the electron energy distribution function (EEDF), which can be non-Maxwellian at high pressure [34].

Relation (2.2) demonstrates how the gas temperature depends on electron density and plasma dimensions under considerations of very simplified physical model. Under con-

stant pressure the gas temperature increases with increasing n_e and/or L . Therefore, low-density small-sized plasmas have usually smaller gas temperature compared to their large density and large size counterparts; but the situation is more complicated as the electron temperature is not independent on plasma dimensions and as the electron temperature increases with decreasing plasma size to ensure the plasma existence criterion, which could be breached due to enhanced electron losses in the case of small-dimensional plasma [30].

There are many ways, which are often combined together, to produce non-LTE plasma at atmospheric pressure, for example:

- (a) Applying alternating and/or pulsed voltage with high enough frequency to avoid thermalization of plasma by fast temporal changes of discharge parameters.
- (b) Enhance heat transfer by increase of convective cooling or another types of cooling (e.g. lower temperature of electrodes).
- (c) Reducing n_e by placing dielectric material between the electrodes.
- (d) Keeping the plasma dimensions small (according to relation 2.2).

Atmospheric pressure non-LTE plasma can be produced by many types of electrical discharges; for more information, see [21, 35]. This work is dedicated to two non-LTE plasma sources: dielectric barrier radiofrequency jet and gliding arc discharge.

2.2 Instabilities of low-temperature plasmas

We can usually determine if plasma is stable or unstable to small perturbations. In the first case the perturbations are damped. In non-equilibrium plasmas sustain the balance of excitation and relaxation processes the difference between electron temperature T_e , vibrational temperature of molecules T_{vib} and average translation (gas) temperature of heavy species T_h in the following order: $T_e \gg T_{\text{vib}} \gg T_h$. According to A. Fridman *et al.* [36]: “The most serious instabilities of non-thermal, non-equilibrium plasmas are related to the system’s tendency to restore thermodynamic quasi-equilibrium between different degrees of freedom ... balance (of excitation and relaxation processes) is stable only at specific range of discharge parameters (low pressures, low specific energy inputs, and low specific powers). Beyond this range, relaxation processes become unstable; their rates increase in self-accelerating way that leads to decay of the non-equilibrium system and restoration of thermodynamic quasi equilibrium ... Small fluctuations of the plasma parameters beyond this stability range can increase exponentially, resulting in the discharge transition into a non-homogeneous form.” The fact that small fluctuations of the plasma parameters can result in rapid change in discharge parameters must be emphasized at this point. However, the discharge transition does not always lead to quasi-equilibrium plasma. There are many examples of non-equilibrium plasma instabilities (see [15, 37–41]) that result in non-thermal non-equilibrium plasma.

2.2.1 Radial contraction of plasma

Confinement of plasma in form of thin channel(s) with finite volume is matter-of-course property of many atmospheric pressure discharges. However, for low-pressure discharges,

the situation may be different. Pioneer of plasma physics Irving Langmuir, who was looking for a word for the main part of the low-pressure discharge, was impressed by the characteristic that the glowing part of the low-pressure discharge molded itself to any shape into which the tube was formed, so he (familiar with Greek and etymology) probably choose the word plasma (Greek $\piλάσμα$), because it means a thing moulded or formed [42–44]. This molding of homogeneous positive plasma column into various shapes of vacuum tubes is an extraordinary property of low-pressure discharges. However, already before Langmuir’s introduction of word plasma, Stark observed and in 1902 published (see Fig. 2.1) the following: “The positive light column does not always fill the whole available discharge tube cross-section, this applies to higher pressures in particular ... Under constant gas pressure the cross-section of the positive light column increases with increasing current. The regularity of this phenomenon is not yet studied. At constant current the cross-section increases if the pressure decreases; under high pressure the positive light column bores into the gas as a thin canal between anode and cathode, under low pressure as a rule it fills all the cross-section of the discharge tube. It is not yet known how the cross-section of the positive light column depends on the gas pressure” [40, 45].

Figure 2.1: Diffuse (top) and contracted (bottom) discharges; picture from [45].

Stark observed effect that is nowadays known as radial contraction of plasma column. Contraction is plasma “self-compression” into one or several bright filaments [36]. Related phenomenon is filamentation⁴, which is the breaking up of a single filament into two or many filaments [46]. In laboratory plasmas, plasma column sustained at high enough pressure or high enough current often does undergo radial contraction. From this reason its glow usually⁵ does not entirely fill the radial cross-section of the discharge tube [47, 48]. This phenomenon has already been reported with many types of discharges, such as direct current (DC) and high-frequency (HF), as is demonstrated on images in visible spectral range in Fig. 2.2. The plasma contraction is accompanied by small r/l ratio, where r is discharge column radius and l discharge column length and occurs at different length scales. It is one type of non-equilibrium plasma instability.

In extensive review article Golubovskii *et al.* [40] summarizes many experimental studies on contraction of the positive column of discharges in noble gases and states that in

⁴This phenomenon, which occurs in high frequency discharges is related to the weak penetration of the HF field into the plasma.

⁵Depending on experimental parameters, such as tube diameter, gas composition, delivered power into the plasma, etc.

Figure 2.2: Images of contracted discharges: (top left) Images of the DC helium, argon, nitrogen and air atmospheric pressure glow micro-discharges at a discharge gap of 1 mm against different currents. The weakly rounded tungsten anode is 6 mm in diameter and flat cathode (plane), made of copper, is 36 mm in diameter. Numbers in brackets indicate exposure time; picture from [49]. The positive column is contracted at low currents. (top right) Black and white photograph of a steady-state partially constricted discharge in the Ar + 0.02% N₂ mixture at $p = 50$ Torr and $I = 50$ mA. The discharge was operated in a cylindrical molybdenum-glass tube with an inner diameter of 2.8 cm. The cylindrical tantalum electrodes were mounted inside the end spheres, the inter-electrode distance being 75 cm. The spheres were connected to the tube via 4.5 cm diameter transition inserts. Near one end of the tube, there was a narrowing with a diameter of 2 cm and length of 3 cm. This narrowing served to initiate the constriction of the positive column at this end of the tube independently of the electrode polarity; picture from [50]. (bottom) Atmospheric pressure surface-wave sustained discharge at 915 MHz in a 12 mm diameter tube with 0.5 slm gas flow. The higher the noble gas mass, i.e., the lower its thermal conductivity (see table 2.2), the more contracted it is, Xe being more contracted than Ar, which is more contracted than Ne; picture from [51].

Table 2.2: The thermal conductivity in $10^{-2} \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ of gases calculated at the ambient temperature 300 K [46]

He	N ₂	Ne	Ar	Kr	Xe
20.7	2.6	3.4	1.7	1	0.6

general all of the contraction phenomena can be described using diffusion-recombination model of the discharge. Extra losses of charged particles due to volume recombination are usually characteristic attribute of radially contracted discharges. If the rate of recombination substitutes the rate of diffusion at some point in space, the plasma does not fill the whole discharge tube and contracts. Transition between diffusive and contracted mode and its relationship to discharge parameters can be exactly quantitatively determined, but the exact solution depends not only on type of the discharge and on experimental setup, but also on chemical composition of gas atmosphere. In the case of common thermal (ionization-overheating) instability that often appears in atmospheric pressure discharges and which can lead to their transition to thermal discharge, the instability mechanism differs in mono-atomic and molecular gases as thermal instability becomes more sensitive to vibrational-translational relaxation in molecular gases than to excitation. Thermal instability in mono-atomic gases occurs due to strong exponential dependence of ionization rate coefficient k_i and so thus the electron concentration on reduced electric field E/n_g (n_g is neutral gas density). Ionization-overheating instability begins with fluctuation of electron concentration and continues as demonstrates following closed chain [36, 52]:

$$\uparrow n_e \rightarrow \uparrow T_g \rightarrow \downarrow n_g \rightarrow \uparrow \frac{E}{n_g} \rightarrow \uparrow T_e \rightarrow \uparrow k_i \rightarrow \uparrow n_e \quad (2.3)$$

The transition from the diffuse state to the contracted state does not necessarily mean transition towards the state of thermal equilibrium, as usually following relation still applies $T_e > T_g$; contracted discharges are often in intermediate state between non-LTE and LTE [46]. The pressure at which radial contraction occurs is often not very well specified in literature and results are usually dedicated to optical contraction in visible spectral range, even though the direct correlation between light emission and electron density profile is often not appropriate [40]. The estimation of contraction onset is difficult mainly due to necessity of high-quality radially resolved measurement, but e.g. Carbone *et al.* in contraction study [41] of argon microwave plasmas experimentally verifies possible condition for the contraction onset in following form

$$\Omega_{\text{rec}} = D_{\text{amb}}/\Lambda^2, \quad (2.4)$$

where Ω_{rec} is the rate coefficient for recombination, $D_{\text{amb}} \approx D_i \left(1 + \frac{T_e}{T_i}\right)$ is the coefficient for ambipolar diffusion and Λ is the diffusion length, which is in order of the plasma radius r and in the case of Bessel profile $\Lambda = r/2.405$.

Moisan and Pelletier [46] characterize the degree of contraction for plasma in enclosed discharge system as the ration R/r , where R is the inner radius of discharge tube and r is apparent radius of plasma filament, which is defined as the radial position at which the luminous intensity has reduced to half of the maximum filament intensity.

2.2.2 Plasma striations

Plasma structures that look like a series of alternating light and dark layers along the discharge current are called plasma striations. The creation of striations is related to the nonlinear dependence of the ionization rate on electron density and ionization-overheating instability (see relation (2.3)) [36]. Striations are able to move fast with velocities up to 100 m/s, but they also can be stationary at rest. In the first case, they are called moving striations, in the second case they are named standing striations. At critical parameters (pressure, current) plasma becomes unstable relative to the radial and longitudinal disturbances. Radial disruptions lead to discharge contraction, longitudinal disruptions lead to plasma striations [40]. The principal role of propagation of striations above 10 mTorr is played by change in the ionization rate in the plasma, in this case main waves causing the stratification can be therefore called ionization waves [37, 53]. Stratification of low-pressure glow-discharge positive column was one of first structures observed in laboratory plasmas, already Faraday observed probably this phenomenon. Self-excited striations exist in discharge spontaneously, without attempts to produce them by external means. However, striations can be produced also artificially [37]. Striations have been reported with many types of discharges, such as direct current [54], pulsed [55] or high frequency [56], as is demonstrated on images in visible spectral range in Fig. 2.4. Striations can be observed in both non-constricted and constricted discharge; fast transition to the contracted state is accompanied by the appearance of striations as well. The scaling laws suggest similarity between striations in micro-discharges and classical glow discharges. Self-excited moving striations have been observed in DC discharges in rare gases over wide range of pressures p and currents I , for various radius of discharge tube R . The scaling laws allow to investigate different states of plasma using parameters pR and p/I as for neon shows Fig. 2.3. Striations exist between the high-current boundary (called Pupp, curve 1 in Fig. 2.3) and the low-current boundaries (curves 2 and 3 in Fig. 2.3). The region IV between curve BC and the Pupp boundary corresponds to a constricted and stratified discharge [53]. Overview about both experimental and theoretical research on striations can be found e.g. in early publications of Pekarek [37] or more recent review paper of Kolobov [53]. Many types of striations eg. in contracted atmospheric pressure discharges are still not fully explored and understood.

Figure 2.3: Different states of positive column in a dc discharge in neon [37, 53, 57, 58]

Figure 2.4: Images of various striated discharges: (top left) Striations in a low-Pressure 2.5 mbar RF-driven argon plasma, distance between electrodes 30 cm. Images of the discharge taken at different frequencies, top to bottom: 70 MHz, 29 MHz, 6 MHz, 4.2 MHz, and 3.7 MHz with 8, 9, 10, 11, and 12 striations; picture from [56]. (top right) Evolution of the striated discharge patterns at nitrogen flow rates of (a) 5 l/m, (b) 6 l/m, (c) 7 l/m, and (d) 8 l/m, (e) is a plot that shows the distance between the striated patterns obtained from the alternating current plasma jet corresponding to (b)-(d); picture from [59]. (bottom left) Striated channel of single micro-discharge (gate, 400 ns) in dielectric barrier discharge in argon at atmospheric pressure. The gate of iCCD picture was $17\ \mu\text{m}$. The argon flow rate was 150 sccm; picture from [60]. (bottom right) Helium atmospheric pressure glow discharges formed between a top pin electrode and a bottom plate electrode in (a) homogeneous mode, (b) striation mode, and (c) asymmetric striation mode. Discharge is ignited using sinusoidal high-voltage power supply of 1–10 kV and 10–100 kHz; picture from [61].

2.2.3 Plasma self-organization

There are many different ways how to define self-organization; Hermann Haken, who is the father of synergetics - the general science of self-organization, defines it as follows [62]: “Self-organization is the spontaneous often seemingly purposeful formation of spatial, temporal, spatio-temporal structures or functions in systems composed of few or many components”. The appearance of structures is generally linked to the changes in the symmetry of the system [63]. Self-organization phenomena can be found in biology (e.g. human brain can be considered as self-organizing system [1]), chemistry (e.g. Belousov-Zhabotinsky reaction [64]), astrophysics (e.g. galaxy formation [65]) and so on.

Plasma, as many particle system with a very large number of degrees of freedom and with long-range effects of electromagnetic interaction of plasma particles with each other, exhibits almost always tendency for self-organization [10]. Previously discussed instabilities – discharge contraction (see Fig. 2.2) and striations (see Fig. 2.4) are both manifestation of plasma self-organization. Another examples of self-organization in low-temperature discharges are shown in Fig. 2.5. Spectacular spontaneous formation of plasma crystals in dusty plasmas should be mentioned at this point, too [66–68].

Plasma instabilities and therefore self-organization can be divided into two groups [10]:

- non-specific instabilities – they are associated with the specific features of plasma only slightly and appear also in another media, an example is thermal (Joule) instability.
- specific instabilities – they are strongly associated with plasma properties, does not appear in another media, an example are plasma striations (see subsection 2.2.2).

Self-organization processes can be divided into three groups [10]:

- large scale – with characteristic scale $\Psi_1 \sim (10^{-2} - 1)L$;
- fine scale – with characteristic scale $\Psi_3 \sim (1 - 10)\text{MAX}(\lambda_D, r_L)$;
- medium scale – with characteristic scale Ψ_2 , whose scales are in the range $\Psi_1 < \Psi_2 < \Psi_3$,

where L is the characteristic plasma dimension, λ_D is the Debye radius and r_L is the characteristic Larmor radius of the electrons for magnetized plasmas.

Figure 2.5: Images of self-organized plasma discharges: (top left) Self-organized patterns of cathodic spots in DC glow micro-discharge operated in krypton in cylindrical discharge vessel, pressure 150 Torr; picture from [69]. (top center) Self-organized patterns in an atmospheric pressure dielectric barrier discharge helium plasma jet operated at frequency of 48 kHz and a flow rate of $0.32 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$. The sizes of the discharge system with a rectangular cross-section and the peak applied voltages are (a) $5 \times 17 \text{ mm}^2$ and 3.7 kV, (b) $5 \times 29 \text{ mm}^2$ and 4.0 kV, and (c) $5 \times 49 \text{ mm}^2$ and 4.2 kV; picture from [70]. (top right) Spiral patterns appearing in dielectric barrier discharge in mixture of air and argon. The exposure time of standard photographs is 40 ms. Experimental parameters: Applied voltage $U = 4.2 \text{ kV}$, voltage frequency $f = 62.5 \text{ kHz}$, gas pressure $p = 380 \text{ Torr}$, discharge gap $d = 2 \text{ mm}$, air content of 4%; picture from [71]. (bottom left) Self-organization and similarity between filaments in non-thermal atmospheric pressure plasma jets: Side view photographs (6 ms exposure time) of the active zone of (a),(b) the RF plasma jet and (c),(d) the MW plasma jet at (a),(c) stationary conditions and (b),(d) revolving modes; picture from [72]. (bottom center) Self-organized filaments, stationary striations, and spherical non-uniformities (b)–(i) in atmospheric pressure argon microwave (900 MHz) excited micro-discharge based on a micro-strip split-ring resonator (a) within a $120 \mu\text{m}$ gap between two coplanar electrodes using 0.5–2 W of power; picture from [73]. (bottom right) Typical photography of self-organized stationary periodic patterns for two different driving voltages in planar low temperature DC gas-discharge system, which operates in helium gas at $p = 90 \text{ hPa}$ with a high ohmic barrier, distance between electrodes 4.5 mm; picture from [74].

2.3 Non-thermal atmospheric pressure plasma jet

Non-thermal Atmospheric Pressure Plasma Jets⁶ (ntAPPJs) have attracted increasing attention of researchers in recent years, as is demonstrated in the increasing number of publications in Fig. 2.6. They are advantageous due to their small dimensions⁷ and have beneficial potential of low-pressure atmospheric plasmas. NtAPPJs usually generate plasma in open space, i.e. there is no need of metal discharge chamber with vacuum pumps and equipment as is the case for low-pressure plasma systems. Moreover they can be used for direct treatment at atmospheric pressure. In principle there is no limitation on the size and shape of treated object by employing large area step by step treatment using 2D or 3D computer numerical control positioning system. This makes them promising tool for a wide range of applications such as plasma medicine and bio-applications [77–85] or material deposition [33,86–90]. Research on ntAPPJs already led to novel commercial devices, such as the kINPen MED plasma jet (neoplas tools GmbH, Greifswald, Germany) [91]. Nevertheless, research on ntAPPJs lacks detailed diagnostics, which is necessary for better understanding of involved physical and chemical processes and for further optimization of ntAPPJs operation.

Figure 2.6: Motivation: The number of journal publications per year containing the keyword “Plasma Jet” in the title of the article from 1990 to 2013. Data available on November 17, 2014. Source: Google Scholar database.

Lu *et al.* [92] describe thoroughly various types of ntAPPJs and classifies them into four main categories, i.e. (I) dielectric-free electrode (DFE) jets, (II) dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) jets, (III) DBD-like jets and (IV) single electrode (SE) jets. Lu *et al.* don’t deal with microwave excited jets, which belong to another category with usually higher gas temperature. This thesis deals further with ntAPPJ DBD jet. There exist various configurations of this kind of jet as can be seen in Fig. 2.7, the relevant one for this work is jet (a) in this figure. It consists of a dielectric tube with two metal ring

⁶Also often referred to as atmospheric pressure non-equilibrium plasma jets (APNP-Js) or plasma pencils [75,76].

⁷Small distance between electrodes of ntAPPJs gives the possibility to operate at atmospheric pressure.

electrodes on the outer side of the tube. Plasma of DBD ntAPPJs is often considered as micro-plasma⁸. This term is used to describe discharges with dimension in the range of a few micrometers up to few millimeters, so they are at least one order of magnitude smaller than the common low-pressure and low-temperature plasma discharges [94]. DBD discharges⁹ are generally characterized by the presence of at least one dielectric insulating layer in contact with the plasma discharge between two planar or cylindrical electrodes that are connected to an AC or pulsed power supply [95]. First investigations on DBDs for ozone generation were performed by Werner von Siemens in 1857 [96]. Nowadays, DBDs have many practical applications such as large-area flat plasma display panels [97] and they are also tested for another purposes e.g. plasma oxidation [98] (see works [99–101] for detailed overview on DBD applications). To transport current other than capacitive in the gap of DBD the electric field has to be high enough to cause breakdown in the gas. In most cases the dielectric limits the average current density in the gas space. It thus acts as a ballast, which does not consume energy in ideal case. Preferred materials for the dielectric are glass or silica glass, ceramic or thin polymer layers. Current limitation by the dielectric becomes less effective at high frequencies, so DBDs are usually operated between line frequency (≈ 50 Hz) and frequency of approximately 10 MHz [102]. When the electric field in the DBD gap is high enough for discharge breakdown, a large number of micro-discharges are observed at atmospheric pressure in most of the gases. Detailed electrical characteristics and breakdown phenomena of DBDs are out of scope of this work, for more information, see [95, 100, 102].

Self-organized stable or dynamic filamentary structures have been observed in various types of DBDs [70, 71, 95, 103–108]. The classical understanding of stable filamentary structures in DBDs is that the “memory” charges deposited by previous filament on dielectrics are responsible for the ignition of a new discharge at the same location [109]. Among plasmas where the self-organized behaviour was observed, are DBD ntAPPJs as well [70, 110]. This work focuses on self-organization and striation phenomena of filamentary radio-frequency (RF) ntAPPJ (Fig. 2.7(a)) operating in noble gases. This jet exhibits itself both dynamic and static regular self-organized patterns of contracted plasma filaments as was reported for argon gas by J. Schäfer *et al.* [72, 111, 112] at Leibniz Institute for Plasma Science and Technology (INP) in Greifswald; regular arrangements of filaments were observed in dependence on plasma conditions. Overview of these self-organized patterns is shown in Fig. 2.8 and colour images of this phenomenon can be seen also on bottom left picture in Fig. 2.5. Self-organized filaments are located at equidistant location around the inner wall of the capillary of ntAPPJ. Two typical self-organized modes of n filaments are: stationary SM_n and locked modes LM_n . Filaments in S modes don’t change position in the capillary, while L modes are characterized by a steady rotation of the helically twisted filaments with a rotation axis in the center of the capillary. Modes occur depending on plasma conditions (RF power P and Ar flow Q) as can be seen in operating diagram in Fig. 2.8 with characteristic operating curves [112].

This PhD work extends these studies [72, 111, 112] and was performed at INP in the same group using the same ntAPPJ during several research stays. While the argon is arguably the most important for the applications, the wide range of relative atomic masses of the stable noble gases (He 4.0, Ne 20.2, Ar 40.0, Kr 83.8, Xe 131.3) makes the investigation of instabilities in other noble gases essential to attain a deeper understanding of complex involved processes. That’s why this work extends the investigation of ntAPPJ to other

⁸Micro-scaled APPJs are then labeled by abbreviation μ APPJs [93].

⁹Also often referred to as barrier or silent discharges (SDs).

noble gases (He, Ne, Kr).

2.4 Gliding arc

Gliding arc¹⁰ (GA) is similar to well known stable arc discharge [113], which is a typical example of LTE plasma. Stable arc can be easily produced by applying voltage (DC, AC, or pulsed) high enough for gas electrical breakdown to occur between two electrodes. After breakdown, electric current starts to flow in previously non-conductive working gas. Due to its electrical resistance, the plasma channel is intensively Ohmically heated and the difference in mass densities of the heavy heated gas particles in the discharge column and the cold surrounding atmosphere gives rise to buoyant force. Buoyancy lifts the arc and in the case of perpendicular orientation of gravity to the arc channel column, it assumes a typical arc-like curved shape between two fixed points [114]. However in some (typically slanted) geometries and configurations of electrodes, the plasma channel starts to slide along electrodes and thus forming a gliding arc [115]. Hence, gliding arc requires electrodes geometry which enables the movement of the plasma channel. This movement can be caused by (i) gravity-dependent buoyant force originating from the temperature difference between the hot plasma channel and cold surrounding atmosphere, and/or (ii) drag of gas which typically comes from below (see Fig. 2.9). Buoyant force acting on discharge

¹⁰This type of discharge is also often marked as glide arc or GlidArc.

Figure 2.7: Schematics of many different configurations of DBD plasma jets, picture taken from [92].

Figure 2.8: (top) Nomenclature of the self-organized regimes in the ntAPPJs. The stationary modes (SM_n) alternate with locked modes (LM_n). The images have been taken at the exposure 1 ms at both axial and radial views (digital camera μ -800, Olympus); picture from [112]. (bottom) Operating diagram of self-organized modes in RF jet; picture from [112].

depends on properties of gas used, as well as on gravity environment. Gliding arc is usually studied in flow regimes with relatively high flow rates (≈ 1 m/s), which govern the discharge dynamics, especially the speed of the plasma column movement [116–118]. In such case, the buoyancy plays only a minor role and the gas drag dominates. Therefore, to study the buoyancy effects, the gravity level should be increased [16].

Figure 2.9: (left) The schematic drawing of gliding arc discharge in most common configuration (side view). The orientation of gravity is in this \downarrow direction. The plasma channel is showed for three brief time periods. (right) Phases of gliding arc evolution: (A) discharge breakdown, (B) equilibrium heating phase, (C) non-equilibrium reaction phase; right image according to [115].

In standard gliding arc configuration with divergent electrodes (see Fig. 2.9), the length of the discharge channel increases together with plasma column voltage as the arc is moving after discharge breakdown at the shortest distance between the electrodes. According to Fridman [115], who theoretically described gliding arc for high gas flow velocities (≈ 10 m/s), GA discharge consecutively changes its properties from the ones nearly identical to a standard LTE arc discharge at short channel lengths¹¹ to a non-equilibrium plasma at longer channels (different GA phases can be found in right image of Fig. 2.9). The non-equilibrium stage begins when the length of the plasma column exceeds its critical value l_{crit} and heat losses from the plasma begin to exceed the energy supplied by power source. The maximum length l_{max} of the gliding arc channel is related to the supplied voltage. Fridman *et al.* [115] estimate the relationship between critical and maximum length to be $l_{\text{max}} \cong 3l_{\text{crit}}$, however this relation was not experimentally validated for very small gas flows (< 0.1 m/s), which is the case of this work. When the length exceeds its critical value, the discharge extinguishes at its maximum elongation and new one is ignited at the minimum distance between the electrodes at the very same moment and the whole evolution is repeated again and again [119]. This repetitive character of the gliding arc life-cycle with characteristic time period¹² is one of its most distinguishing features. For

¹¹The energy balance of steady LTE arc column can be described by Elenbaas-Heller equation in terms of the heat transfer balance: $-\frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} (r \lambda(T) \frac{dT}{dr}) + \sigma(T) E^2 = 0$, where $\lambda(T)$ and $\sigma(T)$ are the heat and electrical conductivity at the temperature T and E is the electric field strength.

¹²Large uncertainty can be involved in the value of gliding frequency, especially at unstable conditions at specific discharge parameters, especially at very small values of gas flow and gravity. At this conditions, gliding discharge exhibits chaotic behaviour. This phenomenon emerged during experimental studies which are involved in this work; author did not find any systematic study on gliding arc focused on this topic in the literature, even though related investigation on chaotic arc root dynamics in plasma torches should be mentioned at this point [120].

GAs operating at low current densities, i.e. in so called glowing arc [121] mode, gliding arc properties are similar [115] to non-equilibrium atmospheric pressure glow discharges. Detailed description of gliding arc non-equilibrium, thermal and transition regime can be found in [122]. Typical gliding arc discharge parameters are summarized in [123].

The gliding arc has been studied intensively from the point of view of fundamental research [116, 121, 124–127], as well as tested as an outstanding plasma source for various industrial applications [123, 128–131].

2.5 Varying gravity plasma experiments

Varying gravity research is concerned with the effects of reduced or artificially increased gravitational force on various systems, where gravitational force can be treated as interesting experimental parameter. The case of reduced g -force corresponds to microgravity environment, the case of increased g -force corresponds to hypergravity environment. The scientific disciplines which can profit from gravity-related experiments include, e.g. fluid mechanics [132–135], materials science [136, 137] or life sciences [138, 139]. Gravity varying research in laboratories on earth can be performed using drop towers [140], centrifuges (LDC as one representative was already introduced in section 5.4.1) or interesting random positioning machines [141, 142]. Other ways, which are distant from earth laboratories, more challenging and expensive, but necessary for some experiments, are parabolic aircraft flights [143], sounding rockets [144] or Earth orbiting laboratories [145]. Some of these experiments allow only limited periods of experimental time and need remote control, which must be taken into account in the design of the experiment.

At this point, let's talk about plasma discharges and their relationship to gravity. In laboratory low-pressure and low-temperature plasmas, gravity influence is often neglected, as it usually doesn't have any significant role in this case (with exception of dusty plasmas). However, it is well known that some types of electric discharges are highly affected by gravity induced processes. The behaviour of electric discharges in altered gravity has therefore, besides the aspect of fundamental research, also important practical consequences, such as safety precautions in manned space flight and ion thrusters design [146, 147]. The electromagnetic forces acting on charged particles are usually much stronger than all gravitation forces acting on them and so, as a consequence, the gravitation affects neutral particles more (non ionised atoms and molecules). Generally the electrostatic force is much stronger than the gravitational force, e.g. for two electrons the ratio is about 10^{42} , for two ions around 10^{34} . In reasonable external electric and gravity fields, the results are similar. In described gliding arc experiments, the maximum electric field is around 10^6 V/m. The corresponding maximum acceleration of ions is then in the order of 10^{14} m s⁻², i.e. still 13 orders of magnitude higher than 1 g gravity acceleration.

In an electric discharge, the electrons are accelerated by the electric field and collide either elastically or inelastically with the gas molecules. The elastic collisions are generally much more frequent than the inelastic ones. Whereas the elastic collisions are responsible for a redistribution of kinetic energy, the inelastic collisions, namely the electron impact ionisation, are necessary for sustaining the discharge. During the elastic collision the transfer of energy between the electron and the atom or molecule is rather low due to the big inequality in their masses. In many types of laboratory plasmas, this leads to formation of a non-isothermal plasma, where the neutral gas has a much lower temperature than the electrons which are heated directly by the electric field. However, under certain conditions, sufficient frequency of electron-atom collisions can overcome this inefficiency and a nearly

isothermal plasma is formed. A typical example is atmospheric pressure electric arc, where the temperature of the neutral gas (and electrons, too) in the discharge column can reach several thousand Kelvin ([148]). E.g. interesting question is whether gravity can influence the electron energy distribution function (EEDF) in the plasma. Since neutral particles in plasma are colliding with electrons and ions, they can also transfer the momentum gained from gravity (especially at high collision frequencies at higher pressures). As a consequence gravity can indirectly affect the electrons and cause some changes also in EEDF.

Some types of laboratory plasmas have already been investigated in both hypergravity and microgravity conditions. This overview is mainly focused on arc discharge, which is closely related to gliding arc discharge. One of the first to be investigated was the arc discharge in free fall [149, 150] and using centrifuge [151, 152]. More recently, several arc experiments have been carried out in both micro- and hyper-gravity. The flow phenomena in metal-halide arc discharge lamps were recently intensively investigated under varying gravity conditions [153–156].

Some experiments have already been carried out to investigate the plasma enhanced chemical vapour deposition of carbon materials in varying gravity as well. Microgravity (parabolic flight, drop tower) was used in order to stabilize the arc discharge to study the thermal motion of carbon clusters and to achieve longer reaction times during metallofullerenes and carbon nano-tubes (CNT) synthesis [157–160]. It has been shown that a change in gravity conditions leads to dramatic changes in the heat flux as well as gas flow conditions during SWCNT synthesis by arc-in-liquid method. This results in the formation of SWCNTs with specific chiralities [161, 162]. Carbon species were synthesized in microgravity [143] in the 28th ESA Parabolic Flight Campaign. A high gravity PECVD apparatus for diamond thin film synthesis under high gravity conditions (up to 100 *g*) has been developed and a change in the morphology of the diamond films due to gravity as well as the influence of gravity on the most active species in the plasma were observed [163, 164]. A PECVD diagnostic study of diamond deposition was also performed in microgravity [165]. The research into reactive carbon plasmas in different gravity conditions is an interesting topic also for astrophysical research in general. Carbon-containing dust is an important component of both the interstellar and interplanetary medium and the extraterrestrial dust also plays an important role in the physics of the Earth's atmosphere [166, 167]. Analogues of astrophysical carbon particles can also be produced in laboratory plasma experiments [168]. Some laboratory plasma discharges have been used to simulate the atmospheric chemistry of other planets because hydrocarbons, lightning storms and high gravity are present in atmospheres of gas giants [169].

Presence of dust in reactive plasmas naturally leads to changes in plasma parameters [170]. Gravity conditions influence the thermal and flow phenomena within a plasma discharge and by consequence also the transport of the synthesized material. Electrons in the plasma, being considerably lighter and faster than heavy particles such as atoms and molecules, are less influenced by the gravitational force. However, due to electron-neutral collisions, the energy is redistributed. This effect is more pronounced at higher pressures, where the collision frequency is very high and the gas flow and temperature are considerably influenced by strong heat fluxes and gravity driven convection [171]. The gravity conditions therefore both directly and indirectly influence all stages of the deposition process - excitation, dissociation, chemical reactions, transport and nucleation of the particles being deposited. A change in gravity induced convective gas flow affects the nucleation and growth of solid particles within reactive plasmas. The influence of the gas flow and the gas temperature on particle nucleation and growth rate in low-pressure radiofrequency reactive

plasmas has been already studied under normal gravity conditions (i.e. $1g$) [172,173]. Low pressure radio frequency plasmas with dust particles are currently researched in various gravity conditions, too ([174–176]). It has to be noted that the conditions in low pressure discharges are strongly different compared to atmospheric pressure arc discharges.

Chapter 3

Plasma jet – experimental setup, diagnostics and methodology

Verily, at first Chaos came to be.

Hesiod, Theogony

3.1 Experimental setup

Capacitively coupled radiofrequency DBD-like ntAPPJ consists of vertical fused silica discharge tube (inner diameter of 4 mm, outer diameter of 6 mm) with two tightly fitting external ring electrodes. The experimental setup is portrayed in Fig. 3.1. The copper electrodes are 5 mm wide, 2 mm thick and their distance is 4.7 mm. The top one is powered by 27.12 MHz generator (Dressler DTG2710, 500 W max.) via -10 dB attenuator and matching network, while the bottom electrode is grounded. The operating range of the RF jet is typically below 20 W. A coaxial ceramic thin-wall capillary with diameter of 1.9 mm is located in the center of the fused silica discharge tube to provide precursor during deposition experiments [177]. The dimension of the inner capillary does not impede the generation of plasma inside the fused silica discharge tube and coaxial configuration promotes an undisturbed development of plasma filaments in the discharge space. No discharge is ignited inside the inner capillary due to diffusion losses. Gas flows from the top through the central capillary (inner flow rate, used for precursor containing gas in deposition experiments) and the annulus between the capillary and the discharge tube (outer flow rate). The plasma gas was either neon, argon or krypton and its flow was maintained by an electronic mass flow-controller. The active discharge and its afterglow can, depending on the RF power and the gas flow, extend from the discharge tube into the surrounding atmosphere. Even if the plasma is not confined out of the ntAPPJ quartz discharge tube, the filamentation remains.

3.2 Diagnostics techniques

The inter-electrode space of ntAPPJ was optically imaged by off-the-shelf digital camera Panasonic Lumix DMC-FZ100 and by dedicated high-speed (HS) camera REDLAKE MotionXtra HG-100K (up to 10 000 frames/s). Slanted mirror was used to get simultaneously front view and bottom view on the filaments for self-organization studies, as can be

Figure 3.1: Schema of non-thermal atmospheric pressure plasma jet experimental setup

seen in Fig. 3.2. Optically magnified image of the plasma was projected onto photo-diode in order to detect and evaluate the azimuthal movement of rotating filaments. The diode output was amplified and recorded by digital oscilloscope (LeCroy WavePro 7000) with live FFT (Fast Fourier Transform) feature. The maximum peak in FFT spectra then corresponded to the frequency of azimuthal passage of the filaments. Miniature thermal probe Optocon FOTEMP1-OEM based on fibre optical thermometer principle, was placed 11 mm under the end of the discharge tube, i.e. in the zone where a mixing between the plasma gas and surrounding atmosphere took place, to measure the temperature of the effluent gas. For spectroscopic measurements, two spectrometers were used (i) fast low-resolution spectrometer TranSpec 2000 with specific spectral resolution 3-10 nm in specific wavelength range of 200-1100 nm and (ii) high accurate spectrometer Acton SpectraPro-2500i, Princeton Instruments PI-Max iCCD with focal length of 500 mm, employed by grating with 1200 grooves per millimeter. The radiation from the plasma region between the electrodes was focused by a quartz lens (focal length 50 mm) on an optical fibre. Acton SpectraPro-2500i spectrometer was used primarily for measurements with Ne/Ar Penning mixture; integrating (Ulbricht) sphere from Labsphere was employed to calibrate this device with respect to spectral radiance.

The laser schlieren deflectometry set-up consisted of a He-Ne laser, a photodiode, and an oscilloscope (Tektronix TDS 714L); see Fig. 3.3. The laser is classified as 3 A class product (maximum output power of 5 mW) and operates in the TEM00 mode at a wavelength of 632.82 nm continuously. Fig. 3.3 displays the cross-section of the jet with three rotating plasma filaments (LM3 mode); the laser beam passes the plasma effluent perpendicularly to the jet axis. Deflection of the laser beam is measured with a photodiode in a distance 13.5 m away from the jet. The signal from the photodiode is evaluated with the oscilloscope using real-time FFT mode simultaneously. All data have been processed by FFT applying the Hanning window method. Alternatively, the motion and intensity

profile of laser spot can be monitored on a projection screen with a high speed camera and the beam deflection can be evaluated by post-processing of obtained movie [11].

Figure 3.2: NtAPPJ setup for self-organization measurement using HS camera [178].

Figure 3.3: NtAPPJ setup for the laser schlieren deflectometry measurement. The movement of the laser spot behind the jet is detected either with a fast camera or with a photodiode. Picture from [11].

quantity	unit	value
molecule mas	AMU	384.85
boiling temperature at 2 mmHg	°C	103 - 106
flash point	°C	76
density of liquid	g/cm ³	0.87
vapour pressure at 25 °C	Pa	8.96

Table 3.1: Fundamental properties of TTMS [179,180].

3.3 Measurement methodology for self-organization studies

The typical series of measurements was started with rough estimation of the operating mode of ntAPPJ at lowest possible RF power. As setting of the gas flow rate has longer relaxation time than setting of the power, the gas flow rate was set first and after certain stabilizing time the RF power was step-wise increased from pre-defined lower limit to the upper limit. At each step, the high-speed camera video was recorded and visually noticeable (if possible) number of filaments and their stability was noted. The frequency from the photo-diode and the temperature of the effluent were recorded, too. If plasma filaments exceeded the end of the capillary then the laser schlieren deflectometry was employed to measure the frequency of filaments as well [11]. When the whole series for one set gas flow rate was finished, new flow-rate was set, new lower limit of RF power was set and after a stabilization time, a new series of measurements was initiated. To exclude hysteresis, the sequence was measured always in one direction, i.e. from lower to higher gas flow rate Q and from lower to higher power P . The operation mode, i.e. identification of number of filaments and whether the filaments were stationary or rotating was done using HS camera. The rotation frequency of the whole filament pattern was easily obtained by dividing the frequency of filament passage (obtained from photo-diode) by the number of filaments.

3.4 Details of deposition experiment

Plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) experiments were performed with a gas mixture of Argon (9.5, Linde or Messer Griesheim, resp.) into which a small amount of tetrakis(trimethylsilyloxy)silane (TTMS) (Sigma-Aldrich, purity 97%) vapor was added. TTMS vapours were delivered within the inner Ar flow blowing above the liquid TTMS in the blower flask before entering the inner capillary of ntAPPJ at the laboratory temperature of 23 °C. The Ar flow of 1slm through the blower kept the flow rate of TTMS vapors of 0.02scm. The TTMS flow rates were measured beforehand by gravimetry, i.e. weight loss of liquid TTMS after longer operation at constant conditions. Basic properties of the TTMS can be found in table 3.1. Thin films were deposited on double side polished (DSP) silicon wafers, that are transparent in the middle infra red (IR) spectral range. The substrate to be coated by films was placed in the distance of 6 mm from the discharge tube end. Plasma deposition took 15 min for each sample.

Deposition conditions of two representative samples can be found in table 3.2. Deposited films were analyzed with several methods in order to characterize their structuring and chemical composition. A morphological characterization was carried out using atomic force microscopy (AFM, Dimension Icon microscope, Bruker) and high resolution scanning electron microscopy (HR-SEM, JSM 7500F, JEOL, field-emission gun). The sec-

sample	power	Ar outer	Ar inner	TTMS
	[W]	[slm]	[slm]	[sccm]
RF1	6	0.5	1.0	0.02
RF2	15	0.5	1.0	0.02

Table 3.2: Deposition conditions for two representative films prepared by ntAPPJ.

ondary electron in-lens detector enabled to observe structural features of the deposited films at a maximum specified resolution of 1.0 nm at 15 keV. For the analysis of the vertical film structure, a cross-section ion polisher (CIP, JEOL) was used. The elemental surface composition was analyzed by X-ray photo-electron spectroscopy (XPS) using an AXIS Ultra DLD electron spectrometer (Kratos Analytical). The spectra were recorded by means of monochromatic Al-K $_{\alpha}$ excitation (1,486.6 eV) with a medium magnification (field of view 2) lens mode and by selecting the slot mode, providing an analysis area of approximately 250 μm in diameter. Charge neutralization was implemented by low energy electrons injected into the magnetic field of the lens from a filament located directly atop the sample. Data acquisition and processing were carried out using CasaXPS software, version 2.14dev29 (Casa Software Ltd.). To remove the uppermost layer of contaminating hydrocarbons, the samples were sputtered for 5 min with 4.5 keV Ar-ions.

The thickness distribution of smooth coatings has been measured by means of spectral imaging reflectometry (ISR) [181]. The ISR spectra were measured at normal incidence of light in the spectral range between 270 and 900 nm with pixel size (spatial resolution) of $37 \times 37 \mu\text{m}^2$. They were fitted using the PJDOS dispersion model for SiO $_2$ -like materials [182] in custom software as described in [181]. Fourier transform infra-red spectroscopy (FTIR) was configured for transmission measurements (Bruker Vertex 80v).

Chapter 4

Plasma jet – results

Most of an organism, most of the time, is developing from one pattern into another, rather than from homogeneity into a pattern.

A. M. Turing [183]

4.1 Self-organization of ntAPPJ’s filaments in noble gases

This chapter deals with study on self-organized spatio-temporal patterns of contracted ntAPPJ plasma filament(s). As has been shown by former research of J. Schäfer *et al.* at INP [72, 111, 112], ntAPPJ exhibits self-organized behaviour in argon gas. The phenomenon of filament contraction depends on gas properties, therefore presented ntAPPJ self-organization investigation was carried out in other noble gases, i.e. in neon and krypton (all are mono-atomic, inert gases). See table 4.1 for properties of these gases. Experiments in argon were repeated because of reproducibility and because of improved employed diagnostics. Experiments in xenon were not performed due to high cost of this noble gas. However study in xenon would be very interesting because of expected strong plasma contraction [51]. NtAPPJ in helium was not examined as plasma discharge in helium has diffusive character and limited (4 mm) discharge tube diameter didn’t allow satisfactory observation of contracted self-organized movement of filaments using HS camera. Nevertheless, J. Benedikt *et al.* [184] performed detailed study of helium ntAPPJ dynamics using phase resolved optical emission spectroscopy. Another interesting study on helium ntAPPJ is that of N. O’Connor & S. Daniels [185], who used acoustic diagnostics for helium ntAPPJ investigation.

Physical property	Neon	Argon	Krypton	Ref.
Atomic number	10	18	36	[186]
Ionisation potential [eV]	21.57	15.76	14.00	[187–190]
Thermal conductivity [W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	0.049	0.018	0.009	[186]
Fluid density ρ [kg m ⁻³]	0.90	1.86	3.55	[191, 192]
Dynamic viscosity μ [$\times 10^3$ kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹]	2.98	2.22	2.32	[191, 192]

Table 4.1: Main properties of used noble gases.

In given geometry, the appearance and behaviour of filamentary plasma of ntAPPJ

depend strongly on two experimental parameters – the gas flow Q and the RF power input P . Under most conditions, ntAPPJ exhibits spatially repeatable, axially symmetric arrangement of filaments, i.e. certain number of filaments is regularly spaced around the inner wall of the quartz discharge tube. This behaviour turned up to be the same in Ne, Ar and Kr. Similarly as in argon [112], two principal spatio-temporal modes of filaments arrangement can be distinguished also in Ne and Kr: (i) the stationary mode SM_n – static pattern of n immobile and spatially linear filaments and (ii) locked mode LM_n – dynamic, rotating pattern of n azimuthally moving, helically twisted filaments with a rotation axis in the radial center of the discharge tube. This similar behaviour in all 3 gases was expected and was experimentally confirmed. Alike as in previous study [112], operation diagram of ntAPPJ modes was experimentally measured in the phase space of parameters P and Q , however this time for all three gases. Measured operating diagrams are unambiguous, i.e. no spontaneous transitions occurred between modes, however measurement procedure was performed always in one direction, i.e. from lower to higher gas flow rate Q and from lower to higher power P to avoid hysteresis; see experimental section 3.3 for the details. Temperature of the effluent gas (11 mm under the end of the discharge tube) increased with power. The lowest temperature of 41 °C was measured in krypton at power of 4 W and gas flow of 50 sccm. The highest temperature of 288 °C was measured in argon at power of 12.5 W and gas flow of 400 sccm; this is reasonable value of gas temperature in effluent of argon ntAPPJ [193, 194]. Measured operation diagrams can be seen in Fig. 4.1. Apart from steady state SM_n and LM_n modes, filaments exhibited also regimes where the LM and SM modes were not reliably distinguishable or where non-stationary chaotic filament(s) behaviour was present. These modes appear especially during transitions between SM_n and LM_n modes, which is indicated by grey areas in all subgraphs of the Fig. 4.1. Let's call these modes CM modes (chaotic modes). CM modes cover various behaviour of filaments, such as: random spatio-temporal oscillation of filament(s), unsteady extinguishing and appearing of filament(s), branching of filament(s), random bending of filament(s); alternatively not-distinguishable SM_n and LM_n modes, etc. Herein, these effects are not discussed in more detail, except of special cases that are related to plasma striations and branching of filaments. It's probable that detailed description of CM modes could be done together with their division into specific categories, but this complicated task is out of scope of this PhD thesis. Chaotic behaviour of ntAPPJ is most probably not constricted to operation in Ne, Ar and Kr only, as chaotic behaviour of ntAPPJ helium plasma jet was recently detected by J. L. Walsh [195] using electrical and optical characterization as well. Let's comment operating diagrams in Fig. 4.1:

- As neon (top sub-graph in Fig. 4.1) discharge exhibits the least contraction, its operating diagram does not contain modes with more than two filaments, because there is not enough space to accommodate higher number of relatively thick filaments into the discharge tube volume. For the RF power above approximately 9 W, the well defined filamentary structure transforms into uniform glow filling the annular ntAPPJ discharge volume. In general, the diffusive character of neon filaments makes their visual detection tough, as well as the identification of modes.
- Argon operating diagram (middle sub-graph in Fig. 4.1) exhibits the best differentiation and broadest range of SM and LM modes. Nevertheless, in comparison with the previous study [112], the SM_3 mode was not observed. This is most probably caused by measurement procedure, which was faster than in original measurement, as the stationary modes need certain time to establish.

- Plasma filaments in krypton are the most contracted ones. The individual SM_n and LM_n mode areas are narrower in comparison to the neon and argon ones. Among all the gases investigated, CM modes cover the largest area in krypton mode diagram. Probable explanation of pronounced chaotic behaviour of ntAPPJ in krypton is that most-contracted krypton filaments with greatest temperature and density gradients are also most sensitive to any kind of disruption, such as power and/or gas flow change. Generally speaking, very small changes of conditions of ntAPPJ operating in krypton cause rapid changes of plasma dynamics.
- SM_3 and SM_4 modes cover only small areas in form of thin stripes in operating diagrams, it makes their observation difficult.
- Chaotic behaviour in form of CM modes was observed in all gases, however it was more stronger in heavier atomic gases Ar and Kr (see table 4.1 with main properties of used noble gases). High speed imaging revealed that sudden jump from n to $n + 1$ filaments and backwards involves disordered splitting and branching of existing filament(s) [15], which spatio-temporally disturbs the filament(s) pattern regularity. This phenomenon was considered to be worthy of detailed study and is further discussed in section 4.2. Visibility of splitting in neon was heavily observable due to thick diffuse filaments.
- Similar operation diagram was measured for the microwave (MW) atmospheric pressure surface wave discharge in argon by Hnilica *et al.* [110]. Although the difference of LM mode in MW jet, the operation diagram of MW jet shows similar trends of number of filaments and SM modes on argon flow rate and power. Analogous detailed study on MW jet in krypton and xenon is still missing.

The LM_n modes are important for applications, as they lead to increased effective rate of plasma-chemical reactions due to enhanced gas mixing and to better homogeneity of plasma treatment or plasma deposition due to uniform spatio-temporal arrangement of filaments. Stability of plasma parameters between electrodes plays a crucial role for reproducibility in the ntAPPJ applications as well. That's why further plasma diagnostics of the LM_n modes is presented. The frequency of LM_n modes varies with power and gas flow. Rotating frequencies of LM_1 and LM_2 modes in neon and of LM_3 and LM_4 modes in argon were studied in more detail, see Fig. 4.2. These locked modes were selected because they are represented by well distinguishable, broad stripes in operation diagrams in Fig. 4.1. The LM_3 mode in argon exhibits linear increase of filament pattern rotation frequency with the RF power for all investigated flow-rates. This is in good agreement with previous experiment [112], which was performed also in argon LM_3 mode. However, in argon LM_4 mode, the rotation frequency for 500 sccm increases only slightly with the power, while at higher flow-rates it even exhibits a maximum followed by the decrease in frequency. This effect of non-monotonic variation of filament pattern rotation frequency has striking similarity with observation made in microwave jet [110], where filament instability frequency of locked mode has also a local maximum.

In both neon locked modes (LM_1 and LM_2), the filament pattern rotation frequency at first increases with increasing RF power. Later it reaches a maximum and with further increase of RF power the frequency decreases. This behaviour is the same for various neon flow-rates and is thus similar to the case of LM_4 in argon. In neon LM_1 sub-plot of Fig. 4.2 it is observed that for low flow-rates the maximum in form of plateau is broad, while in high

Figure 4.1: Operating diagrams in form of mode map of the RF ntAPPJ in neon (top image), argon (middle image) and krypton (bottom image). In the phase space of power P and flow Q the LM and SM modes form a stripe pattern where the areas (and their borders) follow hyperbola-like curves. In grey indicated areas (key labeled as ???) the modes are indistinguishable or irregular chaotic filament behaviour is observed, i.e. grey color stands for CM modes [178].

flow-rates the plateau gets narrower. The table 4.2 contains maximum rotation frequency of filaments reached in Ne, Ar and Kr.

Figure 4.2: Filament pattern rotation frequency development in LM1 and LM2 for neon, and in LM3 and LM4 for argon.

	Neon	Argon	Krypton
	[Hz]	[Hz]	[Hz]
LM 1	40	19	9
LM 2	41	23	20
LM 3	-	48	-
LM 4	-	19	-

Table 4.2: Maximal rotation filament velocity in locked modes for all studied gases.

4.2 Striations of contracted ntAPPJ's filament(s)

4.2.1 Study on high speed video frames

In ntAPPJ, filamentation effects as well as striations were the most pronounced and best observable in heavy noble gases, therefore only argon and krypton were chosen for further study. Striations are one of the phenomena accompanying constricted discharge ntAPPJ filaments during chaotic behaviour in CM modes. They occur especially during (i) interaction of contracted filaments and/or (ii) appearing/disappearing of filament(s), which generally appear during transitions between various ntAPPJ regimes. Study of striations is a challenging task as they last very short time period, therefore high-speed camera REDLAKE MotionXtra HG-100K with maximal repetition rate of 10 000 frames/s was employed. To introduce ntAPPJ striations in illustrative way, spatially and temporally resolved striation features were visualized with a time-colored stroboscopic image in Fig. 4.3a. Final stroboscopic image results from the linear compilation of selected frames from different temporal points, which have been colored with false rainbow colors and were linearly projected into one image as a sequence. In Fig. 4.3a, observed striations appeared during the transition of the two-filament mode (II) into the one-filament mode (I) in argon ntAPPJ, schematically $II \rightarrow Y \rightarrow I$. This transition occurs as consequence of the antiparallel azimuthal movement of two merging filaments and is accompanied by striation instability of both filaments and can be induced by a little decrease of flow rate and/or by an increase of power from two filament mode. The collapsing filament disintegrates into well-noticeable striated structure; merging filaments have Y-shape. Under unsteady conditions, the resulting single filament tends to undergo inverse process and can split (bifurcate) again and transit back into the two-filament regime ($I \rightarrow Y \rightarrow II$). Similar transitions have been observed also for more filaments, which can be denoted with simplified scheme: $I \leftrightarrow Y \leftrightarrow II \leftrightarrow IY \leftrightarrow III \leftrightarrow IIY \leftrightarrow IIII$. This simplified scheme reflects sequential way of creation/distinguishing of filaments in ntAPPJ with respect to number of filaments and their branching, which can be induced by gas flow and/or power change. For comparison with Fig. 4.3a, similar colour time stroboscopic sequence of steady rotation of two filaments in LM2 mode is shown in Fig. 4.3b. During this experiment, the gas flow in the central capillary was kept zero; the outer channel was fed with argon. Power supplied to the plasma and argon flow rate corresponded to the range, where LM2 mode appears preferably. The range of existence of distinguished locked modes (LM1 – LM4) was described in previous section 4.1. Static image that shows splitting of filament with description of different features (transition IIY of three filaments into four filaments $III \leftrightarrow IIY \leftrightarrow IIII$), can be found in Fig. 4.4. Intensity profiles of striations for argon and krypton, which give closer insight into anatomy of striations, can be found in Fig. 4.3. These profiles show typical difference of Ar and Kr striation length in ntAPPJ. The distance between ionization maximum in krypton is generally smaller than in argon.

Sequence of HS images representing similar aspects of ntAPPJ discharge chaotic dynamics in Fig. 4.6 reveals a large variety of filamentary discharge structures in Ar and Kr during transition from n to $n + 1$ filaments. Plasma filaments are visually substantially thicker in Ar. More complex shapes of filaments and increased chaotic behaviour were discovered in Kr in comparison to Ar. Additionally, striation patterns are highlighted in the picture. From the beginning, single filament in argon bifurcates (Fig. 4.6a), which leads to splitting of one filaments in the Y form. Single filament in krypton (Fig. 4.6b) starts to trifurcate until time of approximately 2 ms, when most unstable striated filament disappears and filament continues to bifurcate in the Y form, similarly as in the argon

case. Observed bifurcations resemble branching of plasma filament in argon ntAPPJ that was reported by A. Brockhaus *et al.* [196].

Let's comment findings on striations in ntAPPJ:

- Filament bifurcation was observed in argon during transition from n to $n+1$ filaments.
- Both filament trifurcation and bifurcation were observed in krypton during transition from n to $n + 1$ filaments.
- All observed striations were moving.
- Experimental results agree with the modelling of ntAPPJ [197], although the comparison has rather qualitative character so far.

Figure 4.3: Time-colored stroboscopic images of the RF argon plasma jet (side view through the vertically oriented discharge tube). (a) Short-time instability of attracting filaments leads to the collapse of one filament and fusion of both filaments into one. The transition exhibits disintegration into a striated structure. (b) Long-time instability of repulsing filaments leads to symmetric patterning and steady rotation of two self-organized filaments (locked mode LM2) [15].

4.2.2 Automatic image processing of high speed video frames

Because of a large number of captured HS videos, the images processing can be utilized to get more information from the data. Evaluation procedure is described in form of

Figure 4.4: Splitting of filament with marked point of bifurcation: (left) original picture in inverted colours; (right) original black-white image colored according to brightness for better visibility of striations after image processing [178].

Figure 4.5: (right) Intensity profiles representing visual dimensions of striation patterns in Ar and Kr, which were extracted from single HS camera pictures (left); colours of HS camera pictures (on left) are inverted [178].

Figure 4.6: High-speed sequences of ntAPPJ: (a) in argon, (b) in krypton. Exposure time 0.1 ms. Colours of original pictures were inverted [178].

diagram in Fig. 4.7. Example of preliminary results can be found in form of charts in Fig. 4.8. Subfigures A & B correspond to argon ntAPPJ, subfigures C & D to krypton ntAPPJ, both in CM modes. All subfigures A1-D1 of Fig. 4.8 represent the bifurcation process as it appears and propagates with non-linear speed. Movement of the bifurcation point is clearly visible as it has different brightness than filaments. The visibility of this phenomena is even enhanced using spatial derivation of intensity as seen in subfigures A2-D2 of Fig. 4.8. Striations appear as distinct FFT signal in subfigures A3-D3 of Fig. 4.8. In series B of Fig. 4.8, the bifurcations occur periodically and the bifurcation frequency is fast. Proposed image processing seems to be promising tool for studying of evolution of bifurcations and striations in time to unveil the complex behaviour of contracted filaments, both in time and space.

Figure 4.7: Time-series processing - procedure: (1) At the beginning, every image is row-integrated according to intensity to create intensity vector. Intensity vectors are then sequentially temporally arranged and plotted to create chart of intensity vectors evolution. (2) Spatial derivation or spatial FFT can be firstly performed on intensity vectors for visibility enhancement of intensity gradients and for discovery of spatial frequencies [178].

Figure 4.8: Time-series processing - results in form of color charts in rainbow colors (blue color denotes small intensity, red color high intensity; in frequency charts in last row, the colours represent non-scaled frequencies), x axis represents time as it corresponds to number of processed video frames (HS video recording proceeded at 10 000 fps): Figures A1, B1, C1, D1: Temporal evolution of row-integrated intensity. Figures A2, B2, C2, D2: Temporal evolution of spatial-derivative of row-integrated intensity. Figures A3, B3, C3, D3: Temporal evolution of FFT of row-integrated intensity [178].

4.3 Optical diagnostics of ntAPPJ in neon/argon Penning mixture

Herein, ntAPPJ generated in neon/argon Penning mixture was investigated by optical emission spectroscopy (OES) in order to learn about plasma parameters. Emission spectra from 300 nm to 890 nm were recorded to obtain information about the effect of quenching of neon excited atoms by argon with the increase of argon admixture. During OES experiments, the outer channel of ntAPPJ was fed with neon or with mixture of neon and argon (six different admixtures of argon from 0.125 % to 3 %), and the inner channel was closed. RF power coupled to the plasma was 13 W. The discharge was sustained in flowing regime with a constant gas flow rate of 400 sccm. All modes (SM, LM and CM) were observed during tuning of the ntAPPJ in Ar/Ne mixture, but they were not further studied.

The comparison of optical emission spectra of ntAPPJ discharge generated in pure neon and in neon with a small admixtures of argon (0.125 %, 1 %, 3 %) is shown in Fig. 4.9. The atomic lines of neon (transitions $2p \rightarrow 1s$ in Paschen notation) and also of air impurities as oxygen and nitrogen dominate the spectrum of ntAPPJ with no argon admixture. There are also molecular bands of the second positive and the first negative system of nitrogen ($N_2 C^3\Pi_u \rightarrow B^3\Pi_g$ and $N_2^+ B^2\Sigma_u^+ \rightarrow X^2\Sigma_g^+$). The presence of air impurities is common in plasma jets, which are not fully enclosed systems. After adding only a small admixture of argon into the plasma (0.125 % admixture of argon), both lines of neon and of impurities

are diminished. Then, the nitrogen and oxygen light emissions are the most intensive in this spectrum. At 3% admixture of argon in neon, the neon lines are almost completely suppressed and argon lines (transitions $2p \rightarrow 1s$ in Paschen notation) dominate the spectrum and are as strong as neon lines in pure neon discharge. This can be explained by the fact that with argon admixture the electron mean energy in plasma decreases [198]. Since the threshold energy of cross sections for direct electron impact excitation of the Paschen $2p$ states is for argon considerably smaller (12.9–13.5 eV) than for neon (18.4–19.0 eV), the electrons are losing their energy in inelastic collisions with argon atoms and are not able to excite neon atoms. Moreover the neon metastable and resonance states are very effectively quenched by argon atoms, much more than by neon ground state atoms [199]. Possible processes are the Penning ionisation and associative ionisation. Evolution of relative intensities of selected spectral lines for different Ne/Ar gas mixtures is shown in Fig. 4.10. Further, the BOLSIG+ solver [200–202] was used to calculate the electron mean energy for direct excitation of neon and argon levels for different Ne/Ar gas mixtures, as can be seen in Fig. 4.10. The decrease of the electron mean energy is by factor of 1.2 with 3 vol. % of Ar addition. Standard camera photographs of ntAPPJ in pure neon and in neon with a small admixtures of argon (0.125 %, 1 %, 3 %) is shown in Fig. 4.11. Analogous camera photographs of atmospheric pressure neon microwave discharge with small argon admixtures (less than 1 %) were obtained by Castanos-Martinez *et al.* [51,203] (see bottom image in Fig. 2.2). They exhibit very similar colour change with the increase of argon admixture as presented ntAPPJ photographs in Fig. 4.11.

4.4 Deposition experiment

Two representative samples were chosen in order to demonstrate the material properties of layers prepared from ntAPPJ using TTMS precursor. The overview of experimental parameters for these two samples is given in table 3.2. As has been observed already directly after the deposition, films form uniform layers and they both exhibit comparably low surface roughness, which has been characterized by scanning probe microscopy. The cross-section of the deposited film RF2 has been investigated deeper using SEM, as can be seen in Fig. 4.12, uniform morphology without any structuring can be observed. The lateral nano-structuring of the smooth films was studied using AFM (see Fig. 4.13). An extremely low surface RMS roughness of 0.3 nm has been obtained for both layers. This property of the films permitted the application of ISR for a two-dimensional characterization of the local deposition. The ISR results of RF2 sample, shown in Fig. 4.13, verify the maximum film thickness obtained with SEM of the film cross-section (compare the image RF2-a in Fig. 4.13 with the image in Fig. 4.12). The maximum height of sample RF1 obtained from ISR measurement is 130 nm. Depending on process parameters, films prepared from TTMS precursor demonstrate a broad variety of morphologies from compact smooth films (presented case of ntAPPJ) to nano-dendritic 3D structures, which can be prepared using microwave plasma jet [17,205]. Moreover micro-discharges under certain conditions provide intensive local energy deposition that can cause non-homogeneous surface treatment [206]. Therefore, conditions were settled for non-static mode of filaments for non-local treatment and better precursor-argon mixing. Note that operation conditions can not be directly compared with argon operation diagram in Fig. 4.1 due to inner capillary gas flow of argon/TTMS mixture, which influenced ntAPPJ conditions.

The refractive index of the RF1 film, determined by ISR, was only slightly lower than for SiO_2 , specifically 1.45 at wavelength $\lambda = 500$ nm. However, the refractive index of the

Figure 4.9: Optical emission spectra of ntAPPJ in pure neon and in Ne/Ar Penning mixture (0.125 %, 1 %, 3 % admixture of argon) [204].

Figure 4.10: (left) Relative intensities of selected spectral lines for different Ne/Ar gas mixtures. As can be seen, Ne lines are almost completely suppressed after introduction of Ar. (right) Calculated electron mean energy for direct excitation of neon and argon levels for different Ne/Ar gas mixtures [204].

Figure 4.11: Optical emission spectra of ntAPPJ in pure neon and in Ne/Ar Penning mixture (0.125%, 1%, 3% admixture of argon) [204].

RF2 film was considerably lower, about 1.38 at wavelength of 500 nm. Since the carbon content was almost identical in both films, this indicates that RF2 had lower density than RF1, which is in agreement with the results from IR spectroscopy below.

XPS analysis was applied for the characterization of the elemental composition present on the surface of the deposited films. Approximately 50 nm of the film was removed by ion sputtering, before the chemical composition of the bulk was measured. Note that the information depth of XPS is limited to only several nanometers. The infra-red spectroscopy (FTIR) of both samples has been applied as a complementary method to the previous technique in order to identify chemical functional groups, and to characterize the stoichiometry (SiO_x), porosity and trends concerning impurities (carbon content).

The FTIR spectra in Fig. 4.14 show characteristic peaks of silica at about 800 and 1070 cm^{-1} corresponding to the bending and antisymmetric stretching mode of the Si-O-Si groups, respectively [207]. A transverse optical mode of Si-O-Si appears between 1130 and 1200 cm^{-1} . The transmittance measurements, that could be performed down to 370 cm^{-1} , confirm the existence of the peak at 450 cm^{-1} that is associated with the Si-O-Si rocking. Finally, absorption peaks at 1279 cm^{-1} and 920 cm^{-1} are related to the Si- CH_3 and silanol groups (Si-OH), respectively [208,209]. They indicate an (in)sufficiency of decomposition and oxidation of TTMS molecules by the plasma.

The elemental XPS analysis using the sputtering of the surface reveals that the stoichiometric ratio $x = [\text{O}]/[\text{Si}]$ is 1.9 for sample RF1 and 2.1 for sample RF2. The same analysis shows 5% and 4% of residual carbon in the bulk and XPS analysis without sputtering revealed 22% and 7% of total carbon content on surface for samples RF1 and RF2, respectively. The explanation is that at the surface, a rearrangement of functional groups (particularly -OH) can occur, and a higher contamination by carbon and hydrocarbons can be built up [17].

Figure 4.12: Cross-sectional SEM micrograph of compact smooth film (sample RF2) deposited in ntAPPJ on silicon substrate [17].

Figure 4.13: Topography of the local deposition from TTMS using the RF jet. Film thickness of samples RF1 and RF2 is imaged using spectroscopic reflectometry (images RF1 and RF2-a), the surface roughness in the middle of the samples RF2 is visualized by AFM, RMS=0.3 nm (image RF2-b) [17].

Figure 4.14: Infrared transmission FTIR spectra of the deposited films. The shift of the main absorption peak ($1050\text{--}1080\text{ cm}^{-1}$) to higher wavenumber indicates a higher stoichiometry of SiO_x [17].

4.5 Conclusion

HS camera and optical emission spectroscopy were used for experimental study on ntAPPJ filamentary plasma source. Fast camera imaging has showed to be fitting technique for time- and space-resolved diagnostics on micro- and meso-scopic ntAPPJ dynamics of plasma filaments. Striations of filaments and various non-steady states of filaments were observed in chaotic modes in Ne, Ar and Kr. Mesoscopic self-organization of plasma filaments in neon, argon and krypton was studied with respect to gas flow and power; this resulted in operating diagrams that show alternating structure SM, CM and LM modes in flow/power phase space. Strong dependence of rotation frequency of filaments in LM modes on gas flow and power was observed. Optical emission spectroscopy was performed on ntAPPJ in neon/argon Penning mixture and revealed expected quenching of neon excited atoms by argon; self-organization behaviour was observed in this Penning mixture as well. Atmospheric pressure PECVD based on tetrakis(trimethylsilyloxy)silane (TTMS) was performed to demonstrate application potential of ntAPPJ. Deposition gave rise to thin films with very low surface roughness (RMS roughness of 0.3 nm).

Chapter 5

Gliding arc – experimental setup, diagnostics and methodology

The only perfection which modern civilisation achieves is mechanical; machines are magnificent and immaculate but the life which serves them or is served by them isn't magnificent or shiny or more perfect or more comely.

Karel Čapek, Letters from England

5.1 Brief introduction

Although there were commercially available gliding arc devices on the market (e.g. PLASMA APC 500 Diener electronic GmbH Co.), no product matching our requirements for testing and plasma diagnostics was available for purchase. That was the motive for do-it-yourself construction of specific GRAVARC instrument, which is simple, tunable and low-cost apparatus. First version of described gliding arc setup was designed by myself, Vít Kudrle and Pavel Souček; and custom made at the Department of Physical Electronics (DPE), Masaryk University, during years 2011 and 2012. The setup was constructed for the operation in both laboratory and hypergravity (up to $18g$) conditions and name “GRAVARC” (GRAVity ARC) was given to it. Device was vastly improved during year 2013 by slightly altered team (Pavel Souček left his role to Lucia Potočňáková). Experiences from construction, assembly and testing are incorporated to this chapter to give hints for those, who would possibly think about development of their own experimental device of this sort. Since GRAVARC was employed in experiments on centrifuge, section 5.4.1 is devoted to brief description of centrifuge used. Appropriate adjustment of GRAVARC setup to the centrifuge experiments is presented in section 5.4.

5.2 General setup

5.2.1 Discharge chamber

The discharge chamber is schematically visualised from the side view in Fig. 5.1. Two versions of the discharge chamber were used during experiments (left and right picture in Fig. 5.1). These two versions differed primarily in used diagnostics and in the exhaust pipe

design. The frame of the cuboid-shaped discharge chamber was made from spruce wood covered by natural mica, that was glued in several layers (in second version of chamber industrial well defined heat resistant thin mica plates were used), which protected the wood against direct contact with plasma. The outer dimensions of the chamber were 27 cm, 23 cm and 5 cm, the inner dimensions were 22 cm, 18 cm and 5 cm. The inner volume of the discharge chamber was approximately 2 dm^3 . The front and back walls of the discharge chamber were made from flat, high temperature and thermal shock resistant glasses, which could resist temperatures up to $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Glasses were fixed to the wooden frame using two plastic holders at its bottom and top horizontal part. Planparallel configuration of glasses enabled easy direct visual observation of the discharge through both of them. In the first version of the chamber, only front glass was transparent, the back glass was sanded from inner side and blackened from outer side to avoid stray light reflections. In the second version of chamber, both glasses were transparent to enable spatially resolved optical spectroscopy measurement in different vertical positions from back side. In the first version of the discharge chamber, the plasma emission was captured from the top, through the L-bent fused silica tube. A plastic sealing was compressed between the glass and the wooden frame so the discharge chamber was reasonably air-tight with the exception of a venting hole at the top. Five meters long plastic exhaust tube with two nozzles at the end was used in second chamber version to eliminate back-streaming of air into the chamber. First version of discharge chamber used only 2 m long plastic tube at the outlet without nozzles.

Copper discharge electrodes were placed on the bottom of the chamber and had a nearly quarter-elliptical shape, the maximal linear dimension of one electrode was approximately 8 cm. Electrodes were made from 3.25 mm thick copper sheet. Electrodes were movable, distance and angle α between them could be changed. However, the angle α remained the same during described experiments at value of $\alpha = 72^\circ$. The smallest used distance between electrodes was either 4.95 mm in the case of first version of discharge chamber, or 4.5 mm in the case of second discharge chamber version.

The microphone for the acoustic measurements was integrated into wooden frame of improved discharge chamber and was separated only by thin mica plate from the inner volume to obtain the best possible acoustic signal of gliding arc discharge. In such way, the acoustic noise from the outside of the discharge chamber was reduced. A thermocouple (K-type) for effluent gas temperature control was placed directly inside the fused silica outlet tube to measure effluent gas temperature (black square in Fig. 5.1).

5.2.2 System design

The experimental setup used during laboratory experiments (under normal gravity) and during experiments on centrifuge (under hypergravity) was basically the same. From the beginning, it was designed and constructed considering the limitations and requirements arising from its use in hypergravity conditions. To ensure the rigidity and robustness of the setup, all devices were fixed to a force-bearing steel frame with dimensions $46 \text{ cm} \times 38 \text{ cm} \times 58 \text{ cm}$ (length \times width \times height, see Fig. 5.2). The frame construction provided three levels for mounting of the devices. Thus the experimental setup was vertically divided into three, also logically separated, sections. Plastic isolation plates (dielectric strength $> 10 \text{ kV mm}^{-1}$) were situated between vertical sections due to security reasons. General description of three sections follows:

1. Bottom section, contained all electrical components needed for discharge power sup-

Figure 5.1: (a) Schematic drawing of the first version of discharge chamber, side view, $d = 4.95$ mm and $\alpha = 72^\circ$. (b) (a) Schematic drawing of the improved second version of discharge chamber, side view, $d = 4.5$ mm and $\alpha = 72^\circ$. Modified image from [12].

ply. This power section, which was electromagnetically shielded, consisted of a variable autotransformer (variac), high-voltage (HV) transformer, HV probe and current probe. The variac was controlled either manually, turning knob by hand, or remotely. In the second case, the knob of the variac was mechanically turned using a remotely controlled DC motor. Variable autotransformer input was a standard AC electric power (230 V, 50 Hz) from a socket via a fuse to provide overcurrent protection and via inrush current limiting thermistor, that was short-circuited shortly after plug-in of electrical power. Its output (0%–100% of input) was applied to primary winding of HV transformer. In such way, suitable working power to the gliding arc discharge could be set, with maximum available voltage of 10 kV. Electrical diagnostics of the discharge was carried out using the HV probe (Rigol RP1050H) and the Rogowski coil current probe (Pearson Electronics), which were both connected to a dual channel Universal Serial Bus (USB) oscilloscope Voltcraft DSO-2090. Three data-logging multimeters (UNI-TREND UT70B, 2x UNI-TREND UT70A) and powermeter (UNI-TREND UT71E) were connected to this section to measure the temperature of effluent gas T , effective current $\langle I \rangle$, effective voltage $\langle U \rangle$ and power P on the primary winding of the high-voltage transformer.

2. Discharge section, included the discharge chamber itself with built-in diagnostics (see section 5.2.1), gas flow control and tools for optical measurements. Digital camera used for high speed videos (Casio EX-ZR100) or digital camera for standard photographs (Canon Power Shot A460) and optical fibre (connected to spectrometer Avantes Sensline AvaSpec-ULS-TEC) were located in this section for optical discharge diagnostics (see section 5.2.4 for more details about optical measurements). The gas input was regulated by two calibrated needle valves, which were also included in this section. Two valves exhausted gases into small chamber where the mixing of gases took place in the case of two gases mixture. The gas was then fed to the discharge chamber via fused silica nozzle passing through wooden frame of discharge chamber. Afterwards, the gas was exhausted through another short fused

silica tube of L shape. The effluent gas was then released directly into the outer atmosphere after passing long plastic exhaust tube, which was connected to L-shaped short silica tube. Long plastic tube was used to eliminate back-streaming of air into the chamber.

3. There were oscilloscope and hypergravity resilient industrial computer during experiments on centrifuge (see section 5.4) situated in the uppermost section. In laboratory, standard personal computer was used for saving the data from multimeters, oscilloscope, microphone, spectrometer and thermocouple.

5.2.3 Electrical system design

Scheme of the electrical system is visualized in Fig. 5.3. Electric components (auto-transformer, an inductance leakage type HV transformer with inherent current limitation, HV probe) were situated in the bottom section, which was electromagnetically shielded by grounded perforated metal sheet (green box in the Fig. 5.3). Grounded perforated metal sheet was also used to prevent electric hazard (autotransformer has a conductive connection between its windings and so does not provide galvanic isolation). Both high voltage cables and connections to the high voltage discharge electrodes were incorporated into this section. The high voltage electrodes were situated inside the discharge chamber (yellow box in the Fig. 5.3), which was of non-conducting material and was tightly connected to previously described section. The multimeters for temperature, current, voltage and power measurement on the primary winding of high-voltage transformer were situated outside of the shielded section, connected with well insulated cables. Three multimeters for voltage, current and temperature measurement were optically coupled to the computer (orange lines in the Fig. 5.3). The multimeter for power measurement was connected to the computer directly via USB interface. The output of high voltage and current probe (both devices were specified by the manufacturer to high voltages over 10 kV) went to two-channel oscilloscope via grounded coaxial cable (red lines in the Fig. 5.3), which was also situated outside of the shielded section. The oscilloscope was connected to the computer via USB. The real power consumption of the plasma part was up to 200 W.

5.2.4 Overview of used diagnostics

Measured parameters of gliding arc and corresponding measuring instruments can be found in table 5.1.

5.3 Experimental setup modified for synthesis of carbon nanomaterial

The synthesis of carbon nanomaterial was carried out inside discharge chamber, that was already introduced in section 5.2.1. A schematic drawing of the experimental setup for the PECVD carbon nanomaterial synthesis is shown in Fig. 5.4. Helium as a carrying gas and methane as a precursor were used for the synthesis. Gas mixture continuously flowed through the discharge chamber. Later, the gas was vented out through fused silica tube, 2 m long plastic tube and a steel mesh filter. The synthesized material was collected inside of discharge chamber and on steel mesh filter. Synthesized carbon nanostructures were characterized using scanning electron microscopy (TESCAN MIRA3, 10 kV)

Figure 5.2: Picture of the steel frame on the left; Assembled gliding arc experimental setup mounted on the steel frame on the right.

Figure 5.3: Scheme of the electrical system for gliding arc operation.

Table 5.1: Overview of used diagnostics

Measured Parameter	Used instrument(s)
Power consumption	USB multimeter UNI TREND UT71E
HV transf. RMS prim. U	RS-232 multimeter type UNI-TREND UT70A
HV transf. RMS prim. I	RS-232 multimeter type UNI-TREND UT70A
Discharge voltage	HV probe Rigol RP1050H & oscilloscope Voltcraft DSO-2090
Discharge current	Pearson Elect. Rogowski coil & oscilloscope Voltcraft DSO-2090
T of the effluent gas	K-type thermocouple & multimeter UNI-TREND UT70B
Standard photography	Standard cameras Nikon D3100 / Canon Power Shot A460
The high speed video	Fast digital camera Casio EX-ZR100
Optical emission spectra	Spectrometer Avantes AvaSpec-ULS-TEC (200–1100 nm)
Acoustic measurement	Standard microphone connected to a sound card of PC

with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy analysis (Oxford Instruments), high-resolution scanning transmission electron microscopy (FEI Magellan XHR, 30 kV) and Raman spectroscopy (InVia Raman microscope Renishaw).

Figure 5.4: A schematic drawing of the experimental setup for synthesis of carbon nanomaterial [13].

5.4 Experimental setup on centrifuge

5.4.1 Large diameter centrifuge

Experiments under hypergravity conditions ($1g$ – $18g$, where g is magnitude of the gravitational acceleration at the surface of the Earth) were performed on the Large diameter centrifuge (LDC), which is part of the Life and Physical Sciences Instrumentation and Life Support Laboratory (LIS) at ESTEC (European Space Research and Technology Centre of European Space Agency) situated in Noordwijk, the Netherlands [210]. Therefore, brief description of this centrifuge follows.

The centrifuge was built in order to understand the impact of gravity in various systems, dedicated to serving the science and technology user communities throughout Europe. A wide range of hypergravity experiments can be performed in the LDC facility, including biological, biochemical, microbiological, opto-physical, material sciences, fluid sciences, geology and plasma physics [211]. LDC allows the acquisition of measurement points in the range from $1g$ to $20g$. The centrifuge reaches its maximum of $20g$ at the bottom part of the gondola. In GRAVARC experiment, discharge chamber was situated near to the vertical midpoint of the gondola, so that maximum relevant hypergravity level was only $18g$. The diameter of the LDC is eight meters. It has four arms, each of which can support two gondolas with a maximum payload of 80 kg per gondola. In practice, six gondolas are available, plus one gondola in the center for control or reference experiments. The LDC is flexible in terms of experiment scenarios, duration and possible equipment to use. More detailed information about LDC can be found in the LDC Experimenter User Manual, which is available online [212].

Figure 5.5: The Large diameter centrifuge (LDC) at ESA's European Space Research and Technology Centre (ESTEC) at Noordwijk in the Netherlands [211]. Credit: European Space Agency.

5.4.2 Description of adapted experimental apparatus

LDC requirements for the experiment significantly influenced design of the general experimental setup. As the main part of the experimental setup had to fit into LDC gondola, the dimensions of the frame of the experimental setup (46 cm × 38 cm × 58 cm), were chosen to be appropriate for LDC gondola (see LDC Experimenter User Manual [212] for more details). All instruments, which were situated in inner volume of one LDC gondola, had to satisfy the overall maximum weight restriction of 80 kg as well. All heavy parts were properly fastened to the force-bearing frame of the main experimental setup and the heaviest parts were placed in the bottom section of the frame. As there were no significant vibrations during the spin, the frame of the main experimental setup was simply laid on the gondola floor and not fastened to the walls of the gondola.

Industrial computer with enhanced hypergravity resistance (sturdy design, fanless, solid-state disk storage, etc.) provided by LDC staff was also situated in the LDC gondola together with experiment. Three data-logging multimeters (UNI-TREND UT70B, 2x UNI-TREND UT70A) and powermeter (UNI TREND UT71E) were placed on the bottom on the gondola floor to measure the temperature of effluent gas, effective current, effective voltage and power on the primary winding of the high-voltage transformer. All diagnostics tools were powered from another external electrical circuit (from electrical plug of another gondola) than the discharge circuit to prevent data loss in the case of overload, fault condition and interruption of current in the discharge circuit of the gondola with GRAVARC experiment by circuit breaker, which was integrated into LDC electrical circuit of each gondola. Sensitive parts of the experiment, namely grating spectrometer with computer for its control and gas bottles, were placed in the hub of the centrifuge, so that they were not subjected to high g -levels. Six meters long optical fibre was arranged from the spectrometer to the gondola. The schematic drawing of the whole experiment can be found in Fig. 5.7. Other components, which belonged to remote control and monitoring parts of adapted experimental setup on LDC, are described in subsequent section 5.4.3.

5.4.3 Remote experiment control and monitoring

Some parts of the experimental setup had to be controlled and monitored remotely, as the experimental apparatus could not be accessed directly during the centrifuge spin. Throughout LDC experiments, both computers - an industrial PC (provided by ESA) inside the gondola and standard laptop (for optical emission spectroscopy) in the hub of the centrifuge were remotely operated from the control room using Windows Remote Desktop via ethernet connection. The data from the spectrometer, oscilloscope, microphone and digital multimeters was continuously acquired, logged and monitored directly during each experimental run. The data from the fast camera and standard camera was stored on a SD memory card (high speed one in the case of fast camera) during the run and downloaded after spin-down. The fast camera limited the duration of a high speed video to 13 min.

In the control room, the output of the diagnostics instruments together with video feeds from two cameras were observed on the computer displays. One camera was focused on the discharge chamber to monitor the conditions of the discharge and the second camera overviewed the whole experimental setup.

The design of the experiment was very flexible - it could be operated with different electrode materials, various electrode spacing or angles and with various flows and composition of the working gas. However, the experiment was kept as simple as possible due to constraints of LDC and only one remotely controlled parameter was changed during

Figure 5.6: The experimental setup installed inside the gondola. The gas bottles are situated in the center of the centrifuge [12].

Figure 5.7: Schematic drawing of the GRAVARC experiment. Discharge circuit and computers – black, diagnostics and data acquisition – red, control – blue, optical parts – green, gas supply – magenta [12].

the spin - the voltage on the HV transformer primary winding, that was controlled via DC motor, which was connected to variable autotransformer. The other parameters could be changed manually, but only when the centrifuge was stopped. So that during experiments on centrifuge, all parameters except hypergravity and voltage stood fixed during one experimental run.

The sliding brush of the variable autotransformer was moved by a geared DC motor. As the motor needed only low power, it was possible to use LDC cabling, normally used for analog video signal transfer. It connected the gondola and the control room via slip rings in the centrifuge hub. In the control room, a simple reversing ON-OFF-ON switch was employed to issue the commands UP, DOWN & STOP to the DC motor. These commands were done manually during the spin by the operator of the GRAVARC experiment.

5.4.4 Experimental sequence at centrifuge

Experiments under hypergravity were usually performed according to following, herein in short described, procedure:

- 1) During preparation phase, the gas flow was switched on using calibrated needle valves approximately 10 min in advance before measurement to purge the discharge chamber to minimize effects of the residual atmosphere, the connection between diagnostic instruments and control room was established, the fast camera recording or time lapse photography was started, the AC power of the variable autotransformer was switched on and the discharge was ignited, the door of the gondola was closed, all personnel left the LDC room.
- 2) During second, spinning phase, experiment was observed remotely from the control room, where three active operators managed the centrifuge, the remote control and the

Figure 5.8: The photograph of the installed discharge chamber with operating gliding arc discharge under normal gravity conditions, exposure time 1 s. The helium gas flow $Q_{\text{He}} = 40 \text{ sccm}$, corresponding RMS voltage and current on the primary coil of the HV transformer $U = 234 \text{ V}$, $I = 5.5 \text{ A}$ [12].

diagnostic outputs. The operators also made laboratory logs and observed the in-gondola live video broadcast from two cameras together with security limits (temperature, current, arcing, etc.) to monitor the actual situation of the experiment. The centrifuge was spun-up to the desired pre-set gravity level and the electrode voltage was gradually increased, until the electrical breakdown occurred. The centrifuge was programmed to follow a set of gravity levels (see top image in Fig. 6.8 for an example), staying at one level for sufficient time to stabilize the experiment and log the data. At the end of the measurement, the logging of the diagnostic data was stopped, the discharge power was turned off and the centrifuge was spun-down.

3) In the last phase, the operators entered the LDC room, the gondola door was opened, the video from the SD card was transferred to data storage, the discharge chamber was let to cool down and gas flow was stopped. In the case of deposition experiments, discharge chamber was removed, synthesized material from the discharge chamber was collected and stored for further analysis together with particle filter with the deposited material. Finally, new particle filter was installed and discharge chamber was cleaned and assembled for another experiment.

Chapter 6

Gliding arc under varying gravity – results

The probability of success is difficult to estimate;
but if we never search, the chance of success is zero.

Giuseppe Cocconi and Philip Morrison [213]

6.1 Gliding arc in laboratory normal gravity conditions

This section describes the gliding arc dynamics in four different noble gases (helium, neon, argon, and krypton) under normal gravity conditions. Spatio-temporal evolution of argon gliding arc captured by high speed camera can be seen in Fig. 6.1. For the discharge voltage of 4 kV, argon arc travels during its one full cycle (from its ignition between electrodes until quenching) the vertical distance of approximately 15 cm (individual arcs may differ). It can be seen in Fig. 6.1, that the middle of the arc ascends significantly faster, than the arc-electrode contact points. The middle of the arc continues to move up even after the contact points reached the top position on the electrodes (this happens approximately 500 ms after the ignition).

Long exposure high resolution images of the GAs in four noble gases are shown in Fig. 6.2. They demonstrate the influence of gas properties on the gliding arc appearance for relatively low gas flows. The gas flow and discharge voltage are slightly different for each gas to maintain stable gliding movement of the arc channel. Due to alternating current operation of GA (standard AC frequency of 50 Hz), the arc filament periodically brightens and dims each 10 ms, which in combination with upward motion, forms a typical periodic striped structure in the images and offers a possibility to visualize spatio-temporal evolution of the gliding arc. This allows a direct visualization of spatio-temporal GA evolution with 10 ms time intervals. The main difference in operation of the GA in different noble gases is, besides the apparent color changes due to dominant spectral emission lines, the minimum gas flow needed for the arc to glide (0.4 slm for He, 0.15 slm for Ne, and 0 slm for Ar and Kr). The maximum height achieved by the arc before its extinguishing also differs. The shape and the maximum distance traveled by the gliding arc can be directly estimated from the images. The GA in argon and krypton easily extends above the electrode region. This is caused by lower ionization potential of heavier inert gases which permits to sustain a longer channel at given maximum voltage. The effects of “overshooting” [214], when the low-current gliding arc extinguishes long after its maximum

power has been achieved, can play its role in plasma channel propagation in heavy noble gases, too. For comparison, images of GA in the same noble gases in Fig. 6.3 portray the situation for high gas flows to highlight the influence of gas flow on GA behavior. As can be seen directly from the images, the maximum distance traveled by the GAs is lower and the GA doesn't expand beyond the electrode region. The frequency of appearing and quenching of individual arcs is here so high that the shape reminds a torch. Individual discharge channels, which are more thin, are not very well observable. Indeed, J. Zhu *et al.* [116] reported that at higher gas flows the GA conductive channel becomes thinner and corresponding resistance tends to be larger due to increased cooling. The shape of the discharge channel at high gas flows is irregular and turbulent. The gas flow has a huge impact on regularity of gliding arc. For low or none gas flow, the dominant force driving the gliding motion of arc is buoyancy. However, when increasing the gas flow, the gas drag may outweigh the buoyancy. The drag is most intense at the bottom part, while its influence is continuously reduced at higher positions.

The “gliding frequency”, i.e. the frequency of disappearance of last plasma channel at the highest position and consequent ignition of the new one at the shortest distance between electrodes, might be considered to be one of the main operating parameters of the GA. It contains the combined information about velocity of arc movement and the maximum height reached by the arc. However, under many conditions the gliding frequency is so high, that it limits the direct visual observation of the arc evolution. In such cases, the fast camera recordings or the photographs can be used for gliding arc analysis. As has been shown in the case of a gliding arc in a static magnetic field [131] using particle image velocimetry measurements, perturbations are created by a gliding arc on the surrounding atmosphere; sudden gas heating was observed together with temperature gradients and expanding/convection regions. Rapid localized heating in the arc filament on a microsecond time scale generating strong compression waves was also reported [215]. Similar effect was observed during experiments presented here; pressure in discharge chamber was periodically changing according to gliding arc evolution. In enclosed discharge chamber, pressure changes may be significant. They give rise to characteristic acoustic signal that was detected using microphone, see Fig. 6.4.

Features of a near-cathode GA region in neon are captured in Fig. 6.5. We can see a bright luminosity area located at the cathode surface, which can be considered as the negative glow region, alike in [216]. The place of current attachment at the anode surface (the anode spot) has approximately the same diameter as that of the column, similarly as in [217]. This picture shows that the discharge burns in regime of normal glow rather than in an arc regime. Y. Korolev *et al.* [218] demonstrated that in the GA at low current, the regime of current sustainment in the near-cathode regions corresponds to a normal glow discharge. However, a characteristic feature of high-pressure glow discharge is the possibility of occasional transitions to a spark discharge. This transition starts due to development of instability in the cathode fall region, which is related to the process of enhanced field emission from separate micro-irregularities (e.g. micro-protrusions or micro-points with a lowered work function at the cathode). Then the discharge becomes more attached to the cathode surface and the site of current attachment stays in contact with plasma channel for longer time period [217]. This is one reason of GA movement uncertainty.

Figure 6.1: Time resolved high-speed sequence of gliding arc evolution in argon (argon gas flow 0.4 slm, discharge voltage 4 kV, 1 g) [114].

Figure 6.2: Left to right: photographs of gliding arcs under normal gravity conditions; low gas flow, helium (1 slm, 4 kV, 1 s exposure), neon (0.5 slm, 4 kV, 0.5 s exposure time), argon (0.1 slm, 5.2 kV, 1 s exposure time), and krypton (0.1 slm, 3.7 kV, 1 s exposure time) [14].

Figure 6.3: Left to right: photographs of gliding arcs under normal gravity conditions; high gas flow, helium (2 slm, 4 kV, 0.2 s exposure), neon (2 slm, 4 kV, 0.2 s exposure time), argon (2 slm, 3 kV, 0.2 s exposure time), and krypton (2 slm, 3 kV, 0.2 s exposure time).

Figure 6.4: Typical acoustic signal of gliding arc. It reflects the evolution of gliding arc and pressure changes in discharge chamber.

Figure 6.5: Photographs of gliding arc in neon (0.5 slm, 4 kV) under normal gravity conditions: (left) Long exposure photograph ($t = 0.5$ s). (right) Short exposure photographs ($t = 0.01$ s) of single appearances of discharge channel; letter N denotes negative glow, letter P denotes positive column.

6.2 Behaviour of the GRAVARC experimental apparatus under hypergravity

The mechanical components did not move during the experimental LDC run with the exception of motion of electrical cables and gas tubes. This motion was most pronounced in the case of first version of GRAVARC setup during first experiments at LDC (SYT 2012 campaign) because cables and tubes were not sufficiently fixed to the frame of experimental setup. This issue, even when it didn't influence the experiment, was solved by proper fixing of lines on improved GRAVARC setup, so it was eliminated for experiments at LDC during SYT 2013 campaign. The oscilloscope Voltcraft DSO-2090 exhibited some problems at high gravity levels (higher than approx. $12g$) with relays responsible for range switching. It was discovered, that if the oscilloscope is placed on its back side (i.e. if the orientation of gravity force with respect to the switching relay is rightly changed), than the problem did not appear and the oscilloscope worked properly even at high gravity levels. Gravity dependent movement of optical system of digital cameras (fast digital camera Casio EX-ZR100 and Canon Power Shot A460) was observed during evaluation of images after LDC experiments. This caused shifts of projected image on the image sensor as is demonstrated in Fig. 6.6. This matter was solved by inverse shifting of images in graphics editor. Other components of the experimental setup worked flawlessly in hypergravity, including of-the-shelf components such as multimeters, transformers, HV probe, etc.

Figure 6.6: Gravity caused shift of projected image on chip of fast digital camera Casio EX-ZR100. Original pictures; top picture was taken at $1g$, bottom picture at $18g$.

6.3 First experiments under hypergravity in helium

In the year 2012, during first diagnostics experiments at LDC, were the discharge conditions (gas flow, inter-electrode distance and angle) carefully tuned to operate the

Figure 6.7: Time-averaged images of approximately 700 fast camera frames for low (40 sccm) and high (170 sccm) helium flow: a) 1 g , 40 sccm b) 18 g , 40 sccm c) 1 g , 170 sccm d) 18 g , 170 sccm. The case of high flow and low gravity is visibly different from low flow and low gravity image due to the arc gliding in the former case and stable non-gliding arc in the latter case [12].

gliding arc in buoyancy dominated regime near stationary arc – gliding arc transition. The increased buoyancy in hypergravity induced a transition from stationary arc (Fig. 6.7a) to gliding arc (Fig. 6.7b). The gravity level, at which the transition occurs, depends strongly on experimental conditions (especially gas flow). In this particular experiment, was arc – gliding arc transition observed at 6 g . The experiments where the discharge was gliding even at 1 g were performed, too (Fig. 6.7c). It was achieved by a higher gas flow. However, buoyancy dominated regime and by consequence, low gas flow regime, was center of interest of experiment described in this section.

The graph in Fig. 6.8 shows the temporal evolution of important macroscopic parameters – gravity, voltage and current on the primary side of the HV transformer and an effluent gas temperature – during one experimental run. The gas flow was constant, $Q_{\text{He}} = 40$ sccm (standard cubic centimeters per minute). We can observe that the centrifuge was spun up to 12 g and only then the attempts to breakdown were started. It was achieved around $t = 13$ s. As the sustaining voltage is generally lower than the breakdown voltage, the voltage was a little decreased after the breakdown to optimize operating parameters. However, the discharge extinguished ($t = 20$ s) and so the voltage was increased again until a new breakdown. The voltage was compensated again and after $t = 45$ s the gliding arc was stable and so the voltage $U = 234$ V (RMS value) was left constant for the rest of the experiment. The corresponding RMS current in the primary winding was oscillating around a mean of $I = 5.5$ A. It apparently does not depend on gravity. Main part of the experiment started with discharge chamber preheated to 55 °C by the previous experiments. At time $t = 13$ s the plasma ignition was achieved. Since then, the temperature of the effluent gas gradually increased as the gas inside the discharge chamber got heated by the plasma. Concurrently, the resident gas was cooled down by the incoming gas and by discharge chamber walls. After certain time a dynamic equilibrium was achieved and the effluent temperature stabilized at 122 °C. Generally, the gliding arc heat output could vary with the gravity due to changed convective heat transfer [219]. After spin-down to 1 g (reached at 3 min 30 s) the discharge transformed from the gliding arc to a stationary arc discharge burning between the nearest parts of the electrodes due to the reduction of

Figure 6.8: Hypergravity levels, primary voltage U , primary current I and effluent gas temperature T plotted over the same time scale. The voltage $U = 234$ V is stable except an initial phase of an adjustment of the voltage (ca 30 s) [12].

the buoyancy force. This proved that the parameters of described experiment were set correctly, i.e. the dominant force for channel movement was buoyancy, not gas flow. The effluent gas temperature began to decrease immediately (Fig. 6.8). This is caused by less efficient heating of the gas in chamber by the stationary arc with short discharge channel length. The effluent gas temperature strongly depends on the mode of the discharge (stationary/gliding).

The response of the discharge on altered gravity conditions was virtually instantaneous, so that the diagnostics experiments were done fairly quickly. The described diagnostic run took about 5 min, hypergravity was changed in steps (sequence 12 g , 18 g , 6 g , 1 g), requiring only a short time at each hypergravity level (100 s at 12 g , 40 s at 18 g and 40 s at 6 g). When changing gravity level, the centrifuge was able to accelerate or decelerate very quickly, in around 30 s.

It was noticed already during experimental run on screens of cameras, which were incessantly observing the experiment, that the speed of the plasma channel movement along the electrodes increases with gravity. This is caused by increased buoyancy at higher gravities. The same effect was observed in high speed camera recordings. From frame-to-frame image analysis was calculated the characteristic frequency of gliding plasma channel, discharge channel lifetime, plasma channel movement speed and the distance l the channel travels between its ignition and disappearance (see table 6.1). The time rates of new ignition are strongly dependent on gas flow rate ([118]). It arises from described experiment that this phenomena depends also on gravity.

Figure 6.9: Typical image of the gliding arc at maximum expansion (just before extinguishing) at 6 g as taken by the fast camera (480 fps, exposure time 2.1 ms) [12].

Fig. 6.9 shows an typical characteristic shape of the gliding arc plasma channel (taken from high speed 480 fps video) at its highest expansion just before its disappearance. This is already the non-equilibrium phase of the gliding arc discharge development which is in its final phase. The discharge channel has reached its maximum length. It is apparent that the light emission differs in various areas of the discharge: bright electrode spots (contact points between the arc channel and the electrodes) are bluish but the central part of the discharge is diffusive and yellowish. The visual appearance, particularly the colour and thickness of the plasma channel, also suggests that there is present small amount of the outer atmosphere inside the discharge chamber.

During this experiment the discharge was burning in 1 g as a standard arc without

Figure 6.10: Images of one gliding arc glide at a) $6g$ b) $12g$ c) $18g$ as taken by the fast camera. The time delay between two pictures is 0.01 s [12].

any gliding. In higher gravities increased buoyancy forced the discharge into the gliding arc regime. Fig. 6.10 shows time resolved evolution of the gliding arc in different gravity conditions. In $6g$ the arc is quite round, in $12g$ and $18g$ the channel exhibits higher kurtosis. Increasing gravity, the buoyant force and therefore also the speed of movement increases. This makes the gas flow more dynamic and turbulent, which is evidenced by increasingly complex shapes of the plasma channel. The processes of gas flow, heat flow and electric current flow in turbulent medium are mutually interlinked, which makes theoretical treatment rather difficult and out of scope of this description. In table 6.2 there are given discharge channel lengths for different time development which has been estimated from the image series. The plasma column length gradually increases during one gliding arc period, while the arc length for the arc regime at $1g$ remains constant. The thickness of the discharge channel also evolves during one gliding period. The channel thickness is about 2 mm after the ignition for shortest channel length and increases up to 6 mm for largest discharge channel length. On the top of first pictures of all series from different g levels one may observe the afterglow of the previous plasma column, as it is decaying in the same time as the ignition of a new plasma column takes place.

Figure 6.11: Linear fits to the distance crossed by the gliding arc at $6g$, $12g$ and $18g$ [12].

Table 6.1: Discharge parameters obtained from fast videos: f_g - characteristic frequency of plasma channel gliding, Δt - discharge channel lifetime, v_g - plasma channel movement speed and the distance l_{\max} the channel travels in vertical direction between its ignition and disappearance [12].

gravity level	f_g [Hz]	Δt [ms]	v_g [cm s^{-1}]	l_{\max} [mm]
$1g$	0	∞	0	0
$6g$	7	150	30	44
$12g$	9	110	38	42
$18g$	11	90	46	41

Table 6.2: Discharge channel length obtained from fast videos [12].

time [ms]	1 <i>g</i> [mm]	6 <i>g</i> [mm]	12 <i>g</i> [mm]	18 <i>g</i> [mm]
0	3.15	3.2	4.1	4.1
20	3.15	4.5	6.8	5.9
40	3.15	8.1	12.2	11.7
60	3.15	11.7	19.4	18.5
80	3.15	14.9	30.2	30.6
100	3.15	18.9	45.0	-
120	3.15	26.6	-	-
140	3.15	39.6	-	-

The vertical position of the discharge in dependence on time was analyzed using Fig. 6.10. As a reference spot was chosen the center point of the discharge channel in-between of the electrodes. The results are shown in Fig. 6.11. The velocity of the discharge channel for a given g is nearly constant; similar result can be found in the study of X. Tu *et al.* [119]. The discharge channel velocities determined from linear fit are 30 cm s^{-1} for 6 g (3% uncertainty), 38 cm s^{-1} for 12 g (3% uncertainty) and 46 cm s^{-1} for 18 g (5% uncertainty), see table 6.1. The velocities clearly depend on g level, so the movement of the plasma channel was not caused by helium gas inflow. Taking into account the 40 sccm flow and 3 mm diameter of the inlet, the gas velocity directly in the inlet cross-section can be estimated to be approximately of 9.5 cm s^{-1} . In the discharge area, the induced flow is even lower due to bigger distance from the gas inlet and larger cross section of discharge chamber. The gas velocity in the discharge area can be reasonably estimated to be approximately of 1 cm s^{-1} . This is quite negligible in comparison with observed arc channel velocities. Moreover, at 1 g the arc did not move at all. The plasma column velocity was investigated by [117] in gliding arc with similar geometry, but for much higher gas flows (6-27 slm). In their case the plasma movement (900 cm s^{-1}) was caused by this high gas flow and not by the buoyancy, so the results are not directly comparable.

Each data point in table 6.1, table 6.2 and Fig. 6.11 is in fact an average from behaviour of many individual filaments. The gliding of the filaments is inherently stochastic phenomena and so some spread of the values is to be expected. The statistics of the filament motion can be observed on time integrated images in Fig. 6.7. These are normalized sums of approx. 700 frames from fast camera, which is practically equivalent to long exposure ($\sim 0.5 \text{ s}$) standard photography. Although the bottom part of the inter-electrode area is saturated, in the top part the gradual decrease of the intensity is directly proportional to cumulative distribution of maximum heights reached by the individual filaments. When intensity profile of such images along the vertical axis is plotted (see Fig. 6.12), the distribution is even more clear. The probability of finding the filament in certain position can be deduced from the corresponding tail of the intensity profile.

Theoretical estimation of the overall velocity of the arc channel when gravity, buoyancy and aerodynamic drag are considered further follows. Let's suppose that the rising plasma column can be approximated by a cylinder of hot gas with its axis normal to its movement in surrounding cold gas. This is reasonable approximation in the case of the gliding arc ([124, 220]). The drag equation is then in the form

$$F_D = \frac{1}{2} \rho_2 v^2 C_D A, \quad (6.1)$$

Figure 6.12: Intensity profiles along vertical axis of four images from Fig. 6.7. The tail of the profile reflects the statistics of stochastic filament movement [12].

where F_D is the drag force, ρ_2 is the density of the surrounding gas, v is the speed of the object relative to the fluid, A is the cross-sectional area and C_D is the drag coefficient. Using this equation and assuming simple Archimedes upward buoyant force acting on the cylinder we can estimate the equilibrium (terminal) velocity of the cylinder in a following form

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{\pi r g (1 - \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2})}{C_D}} = \text{const} \sqrt{g} \quad (6.2)$$

where r is the cylinder radius, ρ_1 is the density of the hot gas inside the cylinder and g is gravity. The densities ρ_1 and ρ_2 naturally depend on gas and filament temperatures, which in turn could depend on the gravity level. The temperature of the surrounding gas inside the discharge chamber slightly changed during the experiment. However, during the experimental part, which was considered for later evaluation (from 45 s), the effluent gas temperature difference was no more than 45 °C (Fig. 6.8). Also the temperature of the plasma filament itself does not significantly change with varying gravity. This is supported by the results of the OES. So in effect the square root of $(1 - \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2})$ in Eq. 6.2 does not significantly change with gravity and the gliding velocity should depend on the square root of gravity level.

The approximate average radius of the discharge channel for described experiment can be estimated to be approximately of $r = 2$ mm, the density of helium at room temperature at atmospheric pressure $\rho_2 = 0.18 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, the density of helium at 3000 K at atmospheric pressure $\rho_1 = 0.016 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ and we can consider the drag coefficient C_D equal to 1.8, which corresponds to the Reynolds number equal to 80 ([221]), which approximately corresponds to corresponding experimental conditions. Substituting this values into equation (6.2) one gets velocities 15.2 cm s^{-1} , 21.5 cm s^{-1} and 26.3 cm s^{-1} corresponding to $6g$, $12g$ and $18g$. These velocities, despite being calculated from very simple model, are similar to the measured values. The biggest deficiencies of the model are the consideration of the solid object and the estimation of drag coefficient which strongly depends on shape and on the Reynolds number. Moreover, both the experiment and model exhibit the square root dependency of v on g level.

The strong bands of N_2 and OH in a typical optical emission spectrum (OES) (Fig. 6.13) indicates a presence of air in the discharge chamber during the experiment. Although the helium line is weak in comparison to these impurities, it can not be directly interpreted as a strong contamination of the discharge volume. It is well known that impurities are very strong in emission even in mixtures where their abundance is very low. E.g. authors [222] observed strong N_2 bands in very pure (better than 10 ppm) helium atmosphere. This effect is caused by very high first excitation level of He, which for typical electron energy (less than several eV) makes the impurities much more easily excited than He atoms. Any significant changes in emission spectra, especially in the shape of OH band, were not observed. Changes could be attributed to change of plasma channel temperature with gravity. This supports the simplified treatment in Eq. 6.2. The spectroscopically proven presence of impurities, i.e. the gas of different mass density, should lead to a gravity induced separation of the gases [153]. Unfortunately, in this experiment it was not possible to observe because the spectra were measured from above, i.e. in a vertically arranged way. Similarly, the dynamic effects of gliding arc in varying gravity on OES were also not observed due to vertical integration and rather long exposure times in comparison to gliding frequency. Therefore, in conclusion, at the level of confidence limited by low spectral resolution and virtually non-existent temporal and spatial resolution, the gravity level has not any significant effect on the plasma emissions.

Figure 6.13: Optical emission spectrum of the discharge at $12g$. OH at 309 nm, N₂ at 316 nm, 336 nm and 357 nm, atomic oxygen line at 777 nm and weak peak of helium at 587 nm [12].

6.4 Diagnostics experiments under hypergravity in noble gases

Aim of this experiment was to broaden the scope of the hypergravity oriented research concerning gliding arc in helium atmosphere (section 6.3) as well as in helium/methane gas mixture (section 6.5), where plasma enhanced deposition of solid state carbon material took place. Discharge tendencies in four noble gases (helium, argon, neon, krypton) under varying gravity were investigated.

The main features of gliding arc appearance will now be discussed based on Fig. 6.14, where long exposure (0.1 – 1 s) photographs of the gliding arcs at various conditions in He, Ne, Ar and Kr are shown. Each row corresponds to one gas and each column to different experimental conditions. Photographs in columns 1 – 4 were taken remotely from inside the centrifuge gondola and show the changes that the gliding arc in each gas undergoes with the increase of artificial gravity. The experimental conditions were deliberately set differently for each gas to enable gliding of plasma channel already in $1g$ conditions and simultaneously not to mask the gravity effects by too high gas flow. Unfortunately, due to severe complications (hypergravity influencing camera lenses, shallow depth-of-field, impossibility to remotely control camera during experimental runs at LDC), the quality of some photographs was affected. The rightmost column shows the photographs taken in laboratory $1g$ conditions with gas flow increased by 1 slm compared to the columns 1 – 4 for each gas. Brightness changes between images are not to be attributed to plasma processes but to different exposure times. In majority of the photographs (except for Ar and Kr, both at $1g$ and $2g$), rather long exposure time and high gliding frequency caused an overlaying of many glides of the plasma channel.

The most pronounced differences among gases in the first column of Fig. 6.14 are: apparent colour of gliding arc plasma, which is naturally determined by dominant spectral lines of each gas, the thickness of the plasma channel and its maximum elongation.

The thickness of the plasma channel was observed to be visually wider for lighter gases (helium and neon) and thinner for heavier gases (argon and krypton). The phenomenon of radial contraction can be attributed to the inhomogeneous heating in the radial direction due to finite thermal conductivity of the gases, which is more than 20 times lower

for krypton than for helium at 300 K, and this difference increases even more at higher temperatures [48]. As a result, the gliding arc in helium and neon had rather diffusive character, while in argon and krypton sharp edges of individual filaments could be distinguished. Unfortunately, quantitative analysis of the filament thickness is difficult: for long exposure photographs in Fig. 6.14 the unceasing movement of the plasma channel causes motion blur of several millimeters and low resolution of our high speed camera leads to comparably high uncertainty.

The maximal elongation of the plasma channel before extinguishing was also different for each gas. Generally, the gliding arc in krypton was able to rise much higher than the gliding arc in lighter gases. In typical conditions (low g -level, the gas flow low enough to maintain regularly shaped individual plasma channels) the gliding arc in krypton and argon was even able to easily ascend above the electrodes – meaning that the end points of plasma channels reached the top of electrodes, yet the center of the arc continued to rise up (Fig. 6.14 first column, Ar and Kr). This can probably be attributed to a lower ionisation potential of heavier gases which makes sustaining the discharge easier than is the case in helium or neon.

The influence of increasing hypergravity can be observed on photographs in columns 2 – 4 of Fig. 6.14. With the increase of gravity, the gravity-dependent buoyant force acting on the plasma channel gets stronger, making its upward movement faster. Moreover, due to faster convective cooling, the losses of excited atoms and heat become more intense and cause the decrease in maximum height. This decrease is the most significant for krypton, the least significant for helium. This different sensitivity of each gas to an increase in gravity is the result of various factors, one of them being the gas atomic weight. The resulting gravity-dependent force (the difference between downwards gravitational force and upwards buoyant force) acting on the heated arc channel is proportionally dependent to the mass density difference between cold and heated noble gas. This difference is though proportional to the atomic weight of gas (4, 20, 40 and 84 for He, Ne, Ar and Kr) and so the hypergravity effects are much more profound for krypton than for lighter gases. Also, the thin filaments of krypton transfer the heat to colder environment slower than the wide diffusive helium plasma channel. This effect is exacerbated by the fact that helium is a good heat conductor compared to krypton. Thus, the temperature difference between heated and cold gas is bigger for heavier noble gases, therefore enhancing the hypergravity effects. Finally, the thinner the plasma filament, the less gas aerodynamic resistance it has to overcome during its upwards movement.

In the gliding arc device with the gas feed from below, the plasma channel is lifted up by combination of two forces: buoyant force and gas drag. By the increase of either of them, the resulting upwards force acting on the plasma channel gets stronger. Which component of the force will dominate, depends on the g -level and on the gas flow rate. The high gravity case was already discussed, and the high-flow case (approximately 1 slm above the normal conditions presented in columns 1 – 4 of Fig. 6.14: helium – 1.37 slm \rightarrow 2.37 slm; neon, argon and krypton – 0.4 slm \rightarrow 1.4 slm) is presented in column 5 of Fig. 6.14. The high gas flow influences the motional characteristics of gliding arc as the plasma channel is dragged by the fast moving gas. It was found out that even though this force is of different nature than buoyant force, the main effect on the gliding arc remains the same – the speed of the plasma channel increases, convective cooling also increases and as a consequence the maximum height of the arc decreases and new ignitions occur more frequently.

Figure 6.14: Long exposure photographs of the gliding arc in helium, neon, argon and krypton. Experimental conditions for each of the columns 1–4 (dependence on artificial gravity level) were set to enable gliding of the arc already in 1 g : helium–1.37 slm, 8 kV; neon, argon and krypton–0.4 slm, 4 kV. Conditions in column 5 differ in the gas flow, which was increased by 1 slm for each gas. Exposure times of photographs in columns 1–4 were: He–0.1 s, Ne–1 s, Ar–0.1 s, Kr–0.3 s; exposure times of photographs in column 5 were: He–0.1 s, Ne–0.1 s, Ar–0.1 s, Kr–1 s [16].

6.5 Deposition experiment under varying gravity

In this section, gliding arc plasma [115,119] is investigated with respect to the synthesis of carbon nanomaterial using a methane/helium gas mixture under standard and increased gravity. As described in previous sections, arc discharges in general are sensitive to thermal convection, buoyancy and therefore to gravity. The sliding motion of the gliding arc discharge along the electrodes emphasizes this effect even more.

Experimental setup used for deposition experiment is described in detail in section 5.3. The material deposition was run for a predetermined amount of time, approximately 3 minutes. During described deposition experiment, the electrodes were fixed at the distance of $d = 4.95$ mm and the angle of $\alpha = 72^\circ$. The discharge RMS voltage was approx. 6 kV and the current was ~ 200 mA RMS.

The gliding arc plasma channel dynamics in helium/methane gas mixture exhibited very much alike behaviour as in helium mixture and it was similarly sensitive to the gravity level. Gravity induced increase in the buoyancy of the hot plasma channel, where most of the plasmachemical reactions took place. This resulted in faster discharge dynamics, namely higher gliding frequency [12]. Thinkable hypothesis is, that change in gas flow and discharge channel performance can lead to an increase of processed gas precursor and faster reaction rate. After the synthesis process, the deposit was present on all of the inner surfaces of the reaction chamber, on the electrodes themselves as well as on the effluent gas filter outside the chamber. The fast growing deposit on the electrodes sometimes shortened the duration of the experiment due to its tendency to form a conductive bridge between the electrodes, see Fig. 6.19. During the centrifuge run the filter was heated by the passing effluent gas, reaching the temperature of around 80° C. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the filter with the carbon material deposited at several gravity conditions (1 *g*, 2 *g*, 6 *g*, 15 *g*) are shown in low magnification in Fig. 6.15 and in detail in Fig. 6.16.

Under normal gravity conditions, a network of thin bundles of carbon fibers covered the whole filter (Fig. 6.15a). The diameter of these fibres is about ~ 100 nm (Fig. 6.16a). In higher gravity, compact carbon structures on the length scale of tens of microns are formed without any fibrous structure (Fig. 6.15b,c,d). The deposit did not cover the whole filter like in the case of 1 *g* deposition.

A typical scanning transmission electron micrograph (STEM) of the material removed from the filter is shown in Fig. 6.17c. The material consists of many spherical carbon nanoparticles with the diameter ~ 50 nm. This suggests that these particles, which later formed the clusters and larger structures were produced by a volume synthesis. Judging from the SEM morphology it seems that some of these larger structures were grown directly on the filter (surface growth, Fig. 6.16b,d) but other structures were formed in the volume and carried to the filter by the gas flow (volume growth, Fig. 6.16c).

To increase the contrast between the deposited material and the substrate, energy dispersive X-ray (EDX-SEM) was used. An EDX composition map with highlighted carbon and iron, is shown in Fig. 6.17a,b. No traces of copper from the electrodes were found in the deposit. This means that it is not influenced by possible catalytic effects of this metal. The Raman spectra (see Fig. 6.18) of the carbon material show the typical carbon graphitic *G* band at 1570 - 1600 cm^{-1} and the disordered *D* band around 1340 cm^{-1} . The calculated $I(D)/I(G)$ ratio measured for several samples varied from 0.4 to 0.9, suggesting graphitic carbon structure. Correlation of the $I(D)/I(G)$ ratio with the peak shifts according to Ferrari [223] was, however, inconclusive.

The interplay of the plasma synthesis and the gravity level is a rather complex issue. Gravity-driven convection alters the gas flow and heat flux in the discharge, in turn

Figure 6.15: Low magnification SEM image of deposited material, a) 1 g b) 2 g c) 6 g d) 15 g [13].

Figure 6.16: High magnification SEM picture of deposited material, a) 1 g b) 2 g c) 6 g d) 15 g [13].

Figure 6.17: EDX-SEM composition map of the effluent gas filter after deposition, C - green, Fe - yellow, a) 6 g b) 15 g and c) STEM image of deposited material, 1 g [13].

Figure 6.18: Raman spectra of deposited carbon material, black - deposition at 4 *g*, red - deposition at 8 *g* [13].

influencing the rate of plasma–chemical reactions. Faster dynamics of the gliding plasma channel is reflected in varying reaction time and the transport of synthesized species. Moreover, the strong convective flow in the discharge chamber can lead to recirculation of the gas carrying small particles. The recirculation effect is known in the case of thermal arc plasma [224]. This mechanism could lead to the growth of bigger particles because one particle can enter the reaction zone multiple times. This can result in the production of large dust particles. It is possible that more intensive recirculation occurs under higher gravity conditions in the discharge chamber.

Figure 6.19: Typical image of copper (left) and iron (right) electrodes after carbon material deposition using helium-methane mixture; deposition performed in laboratory at 1 *g* conditions. Left image from [114].

6.6 Conclusion

A new experimental device has been constructed to perform first measurements ever on an atmospheric pressure gliding arc plasma under hypergravity conditions up to 18 g using the LDC at ESA/ESTEC facility. Gravity strongly influenced the gliding arc discharge. This can be explained by thermal buoyancy effects, which increase with gravity.

In experiment in section 6.3, the experimental conditions were set so close to the arc – gliding arc transition, that the change of regimes could be varied only by changing gravity level. The arc plasma did not move under normal 1 g gravity conditions and was stationary. In the gliding arc regime, increasing gravity led to a higher gliding speed of the plasma channel (30 cm s^{-1} at 6 g , 38 cm s^{-1} at 12 g and 46 cm s^{-1} at 18 g) and higher frequency of appearance/disappearance (7 Hz at 6 g , 9 Hz at 12 g and 11 Hz at 18 g). The velocity of the plasma column was constant during one gliding arc cycle in different gravity levels. Presented simple analytical model of the gliding arc plasma column movement that assumes low gas flow velocities predicts that its velocity depends on \sqrt{g} . This is in agreement with obtained experimental results. In conclusion, the gliding arc movement is governed by hot gas buoyancy and by consequence, gravity.

In section 6.5 is described varying gravity (1 g , 2 g , 6 g , 15 g) methane/helium gliding arc deposition of nanostructured carbon material. Material analysis performed on samples collected from an effluent gas filter showed that the deposited material was synthesized in the form of spherical carbon nanoparticles, which exhibited graphitic structure. Gravity had visible effect on the plasma itself as the gliding arc dynamics and the gas flow dynamics changed with varying gravity levels. Surface growth as well as volume growth of the material was observed. Change of the deposition process dynamics in turn yielded graphitic carbon nanomaterial with gravity dependent morphology.

Chapter 7

Final conclusions

It was a great thing to be a human being. It was something tremendous. Suddenly I'm conscious of a million sensations buzzing in me like bees in a hive. Gentlemen, it was a great thing.

Karel Čapek, R.U.R.

The first part of this PhD thesis is focused on the study of the plasma filament(s) dynamics in non-thermal atmospheric pressure plasma jet. Complex behaviour of this physical system with affinity for self-organization of plasma filament(s) has been analyzed and operation diagrams for neon, argon and krypton have been described in chapter 4. High-speed camera and photo-diode measurement were the most used diagnostic tools. Plasma jet exhibits three distinct modes; namely stationary, locked and chaotic modes. Chaotic modes have been further investigated with emphasis on microscopic striations of plasma filament(s), which occur simultaneously with splitting/conjunction of filament(s) during transition between plasma jet regimes. Self-organization has been observed also in neon/argon Penning mixture during investigation of quenching of neon excited atoms by argon. Furthermore, plasma jet was utilized to deposit very smooth thin films (RMS roughness of 0.3 nm) using tetrakis(trimethylsilyloxy)silane precursor.

The second part of this PhD thesis deals with the investigation of gliding arc plasma dynamics in four noble gases under varying gravity. Differences of gliding arc dynamics in various noble gases for low and high gas flows under normal gravity are presented at the beginning of chapter 6. The research on the gliding arc discharge was continued in hypergravity experiments at the centrifuge. The gas flow was kept as low as possible to enhance the buoyancy effects. To the best of author's knowledge, these are the first experiments with the gliding arc plasma under hypergravity. A detailed study is presented for helium in section 6.3 and enhanced by results for neon, argon and krypton in section 6.4. The experimental results for helium in combination with simple analytical model show that the speed of the gliding arc channel movement increases with the increase of gravity. The maximum distance traveled by gliding arc decreases with the increase of gravity as well. Gliding frequency depends on both parameters, thus it is strongly dependent on gravity. This conclusion was experimentally verified also for other noble gases. The deposition experiment leads to the conclusion that gravity influences plasma enhanced material synthesis as the process relies on plasma dynamics. Gravity induced changes of discharge channel movement resulted in different morphology of carbon deposits.

Overall, two different plasma discharges have been investigated under atmospheric pres-

sure and in heavy noble gas environment that causes strong filamentation effects. Camera imaging proved to be an appropriate technique for the study on dynamic effect of plasma filament(s) in both discharges. Nonetheless, more advanced imaging instrument had to be used in the case of plasma jet due to smaller spatial and time scales of the observed effects. Radial contraction in atmospheric pressure plasmas is often disadvantageous and affects certain applications, because it significantly reduces the plasma cross section and volume; these two parameters are one the most important for plasma treatment and synthesis. Moreover, static filaments can cause unwanted local overheating. Regularly ordered filamentary static discharge structures sometimes exhibit dynamic instabilities and spontaneous transitions into disordered, chaotic state. Exploring of the transition between order and chaos is essential for the advancement of industrial atmospheric pressure plasma technologies. In the case of described ntAPPJ, the resulting process homogeneity can be improved by a spatio-temporal de-localisation of filament(s), which occurs in reported LM and CM modes. Furthermore, movement of plasma filament(s) in the operating zone causes enhanced activation of medium by increasing the effective gas volume that is activated by electrical discharge. This statement is valid for both explored plasmas.

Several questions concerning gliding arc and plasma jet have been answered, but many remain to be studied. For example, flow processes and pressure changes in enclosed gliding arc discharge chamber should be further explored, because they influence the whole discharge operation. This could lead to discovery of e.g. Rayleigh–Taylor instability during slow discharge channel gliding due to different gas densities in enclosed chamber. It follows that mechanisms of self-organization in RF ntAPPJ are general and should be most probably present in different forms also in other configurations of RF plasma jets. Another possible direction of the future work is to study the ntAPPJ modes in discharge tubes with different diameters; or to change the wall temperature of ntAPPJ capillary to study its influence on plasma contraction. A detailed comparison between electrical and visual observation would be beneficial for both ntAPPJ and gliding arc devices.

Chapter 8

Annexes

8.1 Curriculum Vitae

Mgr. Jiří Šperka Born 2. 6. 1987 in Brno, Czech Republic

EDUCATION

- since 2011: Current PhD student at Masaryk University in Brno, Plasma Physics.
- 2009-2011: Master's degree in Plasma Physics, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno; master thesis: "Plasmachemical deposition diamond films in dual microwave/radio frequency discharge".
- 2006-2009: Bachelor's degree in Physics, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno; bachelor thesis: "Deposition of nanocrystalline diamond films in microwave discharge"

HONORS AND AWARDS

- 2015: Best student oral presentation in physical sciences, The European Low Gravity Research Association 22nd biennial Symposium and General Assembly, Corfu, Greece; presentation entitled "Hypergravity Experiments at Large Diameter Centrifuge with Gliding Arc Plasma"
- 2014: Best student poster, The XXII Europhysics Conference on Atomic and Molecular Physics of Ionized Gases, Greifswald, Germany; poster entitled "Non-thermal Atmospheric Pressure Plasma Jet Operated in Krypton and Argon: Visual Characterisation of Discharge using High-speed Camera"

RESEARCH EXPERIENCE, EDUCATIONAL STAY

- Leibniz-Institut für Plasmaforschung und Technologie e.V. , Greifswald Position: Student Worker in Laboratory 2010
- Erasmus study, Ernst-Moritz-Arndt Universität, Greifswald 2010
- Hands-On Training course in the Netherlands, Eindhoven 2011
- Leibniz-Institut für Plasmaforschung und Technologie e.V. , Greifswald Position: Student Intership 2012

TEACHING EXPERIENCE

- 2012 and 2013 (autumn semesters): Plasma physics (Teaching Assistant), Masaryk University
- 2014 (autumn semester): Mathematics (Teaching Assistant), Brno University of Technology

EMPLOYMENT

- since April 2015: Czech Metrology Institute Brno, Department of Nanometrology

PROJECTS

- European Space Agency SYT2012 programme 2012
- European Space Agency SYT2013 programme 2013
- 2013: investigator of FRVŠ project 12/2013/G6 “Plasma physics exercise book” financed by Ministry of Education of Czech Republic. (Exercise book was written for students of subject F5170, is available free of charge in English and Czech version. Coauthors are Mgr. Jan Voráč and doc. Mgr. Lenka Zajíčková, Ph.D. Exercise book together with electronic questionnaires is available online at <http://physics.muni.cz/~sperka/exercises.html>)

8.2 Journal publications related to this thesis

1. Schäfer, J., Hnilica, J., Šperka, J., Quade, A., Kudrle, V., Foest, R., Vodák, J. and Zajíčková, L., Tetrakis (trimethylsilyloxy) silane for nanostructured SiO₂-like films deposited by PECVD at atmospheric pressure. *Surface and Coatings Technology*, 2015. In Press.
2. Potočňáková L., Šperka J., Zikán P., Loon J., Beckers J., Kudrle V., Gravity effects on a gliding arc in four noble gases: from normal to hypergravity, *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* 24, 2015
3. Schäfer J., Šperka J., Gött G., Zajíčková L., Foest R., High-Speed Visualization of Filament Instabilities and Self-Organization Effect in RF Argon Plasma Jet at Atmospheric Pressure, *IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science*, 2014
4. Potočňáková L., Šperka J., Zikán P., Loon J., Beckers J., Kudrle V., Gliding Arc in Noble Gases Under Normal and Hypergravity Conditions, *IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science*, 2014
5. Šperka J., Souček P., Loon J., Dowson A., Schwarz C., Krause J., Butenko Y., Kroesen G., Kudrle V., Hypergravity synthesis of graphitic carbon nanomaterial in glide arc plasma, *Materials Research Bulletin* 54 (2014) 61-65
6. Šperka J., Souček P., Loon J., Dowson A., Schwarz C., Krause J., Kroesen G., Kudrle V., Hypergravity effects on glide arc plasma, *European Physical Journal D* 67(12) (2013) 1-9
7. Schäfer J., Foest R., Reuter S., Kewitz T., Šperka J., Weltmann D., Laser schlieren deflectometry for temperature analysis of filamentary non-thermal atmospheric pressure plasma, *Review of Scientific Instruments* 83(10) (2012) 103506

Bibliography

- [1] J. S. Kelso, *Dynamic patterns: The self-organization of brain and behavior*. MIT press, 1997.
- [2] Wikipedia, “Quark-gluon plasma — wikipedia, the free encyclopedia.” https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Quark%E2%80%93gluon_plasma&oldid=668734809, 2015. [Online; accessed 28-June-2015].
- [3] S. L. Miller *et al.*, “A production of amino acids under possible primitive earth conditions,” *Science*, vol. 117, no. 3046, pp. 528–529, 1953.
- [4] S. L. Miller and C. Harold, “Organic compound syntheses on the primitive earth,” *Science*, vol. 130, p. 251, 1959.
- [5] H. Alfvén, “On hierarchical cosmology,” *Astrophysics and Space Science*, vol. 89, pp. 313–324, 1983.
- [6] D. A. Gurnett and A. Bhattacharjee, *Introduction to plasma physics: with space and laboratory applications*. Cambridge university press, 2005.
- [7] J. A. Bittencourt, *Fundamentals of plasma physics*. Springer Science and Business Media, 2013.
- [8] U. S. Inan and M. Gołkowski, *Principles of plasma physics for engineers and scientists*. Cambridge University Press, 2010.
- [9] M. A. Lieberman and A. J. Lichtenberg, “Principles of plasma discharges and materials processing,” 1994.
- [10] A. I. Morozov, *Introduction to Plasma Dynamics*. CRC Press, 2012.
- [11] J. Schäfer, R. Foest, S. Reuter, T. Kewitz, J. Šperka, and K.-D. Weltmann, “Laserschlieren deflectometry for temperature analysis of filamentary non-thermal atmospheric pressure plasma,” *Review of Scientific Instruments*, vol. 83, no. 10, p. 103506, 2012.
- [12] J. Šperka, P. Souček, J. J. Van Loon, A. Dowson, C. Schwarz, J. Krause, G. Kroesen, and V. Kudrle, “Hypergravity effects on glide arc plasma,” *The European Physical Journal D*, vol. 67, no. 12, pp. 1–9, 2013.
- [13] J. Šperka, P. Souček, J. J. Van Loon, A. Dowson, C. Schwarz, J. Krause, Y. Butenko, G. Kroesen, and V. Kudrle, “Hypergravity synthesis of graphitic carbon nanomaterial in glide arc plasma,” *Materials Research Bulletin*, vol. 54, pp. 61–65, 2014.

- [14] L. Potocnakova, J. Sperka, P. Zikán, J. van Loon, J. Beckers, and V. Kudrle, “Gliding arc in noble gases under normal and hypergravity conditions,” *IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science*, vol. 42, no. 10, pp. 2724–2725, 2014.
- [15] J. Schäfer, J. Šperka, G. Gött, L. Zajíčková, and R. Foest, “High-speed visualization of filament instabilities and self-organization effect in rf argon plasma jet at atmospheric pressure,” *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 42, no. 10, pp. 2454–2455, 2014.
- [16] L. Potočňáková, J. Šperka, P. Zikán, J. J. van Loon, J. Beckers, and V. Kudrle, “Gravity effects on a gliding arc in four noble gases: from normal to hypergravity,” *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, vol. 24, no. 2, p. 022002, 2015.
- [17] J. Schäfer, J. Hnilica, J. Šperka, A. Quade, V. Kudrle, R. Foest, J. Vodák, and L. Zajíčková, “Tetrakis (trimethylsilyloxy) silane for nanostructured SiO₂-like films deposited by PECVD at atmospheric pressure,” *Surface and Coatings Technology*, 2015.
- [18] P. Richard, “Feynman, the character of physical law,” 1965.
- [19] F. Leblanc, K. Aplin, Y. Yair, G. Harrison, J. P. Lebreton, and M. Blanc, *Planetary atmospheric electricity*, vol. 30. Springer Science & Business Media, 2008.
- [20] Y. P. Raizer and J. E. Allen, *Gas discharge physics*, vol. 2. Springer Berlin, 1997.
- [21] A. Fridman, A. Chirokov, and A. Gutsol, “Non-thermal atmospheric pressure discharges,” *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 38, no. 2, p. R1, 2005.
- [22] J. Park, I. Henins, H. Herrmann, and G. Selwyn, “Gas breakdown in an atmospheric pressure radio-frequency capacitive plasma source,” *journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 89, no. 1, pp. 15–19, 2001.
- [23] G. Park, S. Park, M. Choi, I. Koo, J. Byun, J. Hong, J. Sim, G. Collins, and J. Lee, “Atmospheric-pressure plasma sources for biomedical applications,” *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, vol. 21, no. 4, p. 043001, 2012.
- [24] J. F. Keithley, *The story of electrical and magnetic measurements: from 500 BC to the 1940s*. John Wiley & Sons, 1999.
- [25] P. Iversen and D. J. Lacks, “A life of its own: The tenuous connection between thales of miletus and the study of electrostatic charging,” *Journal of Electrostatics*, vol. 70, no. 3, pp. 309–311, 2012.
- [26] C. Tendero, T. C., T. P., J. Desmaison, and P. Leprince, “Atmospheric pressure plasmas: A review,” *Spectrochimica Acta Part B*, vol. 61, p. 2, 2006.
- [27] A. Anders, “Tracking down the origin of arc plasma science-ii. early continuous discharges,” *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 1060–1069, 2003.
- [28] L. Liu, R. Huang, G. Song, and X. Hao, “Behavior and spectrum analysis of welding arc in low-power yag-laser–mag hybrid-welding process,” *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 1937–1943, 2008.

- [29] B. Bora, H. Bhuyan, M. Favre, E. Wyndham, and H. Chuaqui, “Diagnostic of capacitively coupled low pressure radio frequency plasma: an approach through electrical discharge characteristic,” *International Journal of Applied Physics and Mathematics*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 124–128, 2011.
- [30] P. Bruggeman and R. Brandenburg, “Atmospheric pressure discharge filaments and microplasmas: physics, chemistry and diagnostics,” *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 46, no. 46, p. 464001, 2013.
- [31] W. Finkelnburg and H. Maecker, *Electric Arcs and Thermal Plasmas (Encyclopedia of Physics XXII)*. Springer Berlin, 1956.
- [32] K. H. Becker, U. Kogelschatz, K. Schoenbach, and R. Barker, *Non-equilibrium air plasmas at atmospheric pressure*. IOP Publishing Ltd, 2005.
- [33] D. Mariotti and R. M. Sankaran, “Microplasmas for nanomaterials synthesis,” *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 43, no. 32, p. 323001, 2010.
- [34] J. Choi, F. Iza, J. K. Lee, and C.-M. Ryu, “Electron and ion kinetics in a dc microplasma at atmospheric pressure,” *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 1274–1278, 2007.
- [35] L. Bárdos and H. Baránková, “Cold atmospheric plasma: Sources, processes, and applications,” *Thin Solid Films*, vol. 518, no. 23, pp. 6705–6713, 2010.
- [36] A. Fridman and L. A. Kennedy, *Plasma physics and engineering*. CRC press, 2004.
- [37] L. Pekarek, “Ionization waves (striations) in a discharge plasma,” *Physics-Uspekhi*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 188–208, 1968.
- [38] J. Schäfer, R. Foest, A. Ohl, and K. Weltmann, “Miniaturized non-thermal atmospheric pressure plasma jet-characterization of self-organized regimes,” *Plasma Phys. Control. Fusion*, vol. 51, p. 124045, 2009.
- [39] T. Hoder, D. Loffhagen, C. Wilke, H. Grosch, J. Schäfer, K.-D. Weltmann, and R. Brandenburg, “Striated microdischarges in an asymmetric barrier discharge in argon at atmospheric pressure,” *Physical Review E*, vol. 84, no. 4, p. 046404, 2011.
- [40] Y. B. Golubovskii, V. Nekuchaev, S. Gorchakov, and D. Uhrlandt, “Contraction of the positive column of discharges in noble gases,” *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, vol. 20, no. 5, p. 053002, 2011.
- [41] E. Carbone, S. Hübner, J. Palomares, and J. van der Mullen, “The radial contraction of argon microwave plasmas studied by thomson scattering,” *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 45, no. 34, p. 345203, 2012.
- [42] I. Langmuir, “Oscillations in ionized gases,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, vol. 14, no. 8, p. 627, 1928.
- [43] L. Tonks, “The birth of plasma,” *American Journal of Physics*, vol. 35, no. 9, pp. 857–858, 1967.
- [44] M. Hirsh and H. Oskam, “Electronic discharges,” in *Gaseous electronics*, vol. 1, Academic Press, 1978.

- [45] J. Stark, *Die elektrizität in gasen*. JA Barth, 1902.
- [46] M. Moisan and J. Pelletier, *Physics of Collisional Plasmas: Introduction to High-Frequency Discharges*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [47] G. Petrov and C. Ferreira, “Numerical modeling of the constriction of the dc positive column in rare gases,” *Physical Review E*, vol. 59, no. 3, p. 3571, 1999.
- [48] Y. Kabouzi, M. Calzada, M. Moisan, K. Tran, and C. Trassy, “Radial contraction of microwave-sustained plasma columns at atmospheric pressure,” *Journal of applied physics*, vol. 91, no. 3, pp. 1008–1019, 2002.
- [49] V. Arkhipenko, A. Kirillov, Y. Safronau, and L. Simonchik, “Dc atmospheric pressure glow microdischarges in the current range from microamps up to amperes,” *The European Physical Journal D*, vol. 60, no. 3, pp. 455–463, 2010.
- [50] Y. Z. Ionikh, A. Meshchanov, F. Petrov, N. Dyatko, and A. Napartovich, “Partially constricted glow discharge in an argon-nitrogen mixture,” *Plasma Physics Reports*, vol. 34, no. 10, pp. 867–878, 2008.
- [51] E. Castanos-Martinez and M. Moisan, “Expansion/homogenization of contracted/filamentary microwave discharges at atmospheric pressure,” *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 39, no. 11, pp. 2192–2193, 2011.
- [52] D. Staack, B. Farouk, A. Gutsol, and A. Fridman, “Stabilization of the ionization overheating thermal instability in atmospheric pressure microplasmas,” *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 106, no. 1, p. 013303, 2009.
- [53] V. I. Kolobov, “Striations in rare gas plasmas,” *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 39, no. 24, p. R487, 2006.
- [54] T. Donahue and G. H. Dieke, “Oscillatory phenomena in direct current glow discharges,” *Physical Review*, vol. 81, no. 2, p. 248, 1951.
- [55] J. Janča and A. Tálský, “Striation of the plasma of a single-pole high-frequency high-pressure discharge,” *Czechoslovak Journal of Physics*, vol. 18, no. 9, pp. 1227–1227, 1968.
- [56] H. Mulders, W. Brok, and W. Stoffels, “Striations in a low-pressure rf-driven argon plasma,” *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 1380–1381, 2008.
- [57] S. Pfau, A. Rutscher, and K. Wojaczek, “Das ähnlichkeitsgesetz für quasineutrale, anisotherme entladungssäulen,” *Beiträge aus der Plasmaphysik*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 333–358, 1969.
- [58] H. Amemiya, “Characteristics of striations of he and ne plasmas in small-diameter discharge tubes,” *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 17, no. 12, p. 2387, 1984.
- [59] Y. C. Hong, H. S. Uhm, and W. J. Yi, “Atmospheric pressure nitrogen plasma jet: Observation of striated multilayer discharge patterns,” *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 93, no. 5, p. 051504, 2008.

- [60] T. Hoder, C. Wilke, D. Loffhagen, and R. Brandenburg, "Observation of striated structures in argon barrier discharges at atmospheric pressure," *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 39, no. 11, pp. 2158–2159, 2011.
- [61] Y. Yang, J. Shi, J. Harry, J. Proctor, C. P. Garner, and M. G. Kong, "Multilayer plasma patterns in atmospheric pressure glow discharges," *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 302–303, 2005.
- [62] H. Haken, "Self-organization," vol. 3, no. 8, p. 1401, 2008.
- [63] M. Bushev, *Synergetics: Chaos, order, self-organization*. World scientific, 1994.
- [64] A. Pechenkin, "Bp belousov and his reaction," *Journal of biosciences*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 365–371, 2009.
- [65] M. Y. Marov and A. V. Kolesnichenko, *Turbulence and Self-organization: modeling astrophysical objects*, vol. 389. Springer Science & Business Media, 2013.
- [66] H. Thomas, G. Morfill, V. Demmel, J. Goree, B. Feuerbacher, and D. Möhlmann, "Plasma crystal: Coulomb crystallization in a dusty plasma," *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 73, no. 5, pp. 652–655, 1994.
- [67] G. Morfill, H. Thomas, U. Konopka, H. Rothermel, M. Zuzic, A. Ivlev, and J. Goree, "Condensed plasmas under microgravity," *Physical review letters*, vol. 83, no. 8, p. 1598, 1999.
- [68] P. K. Shukla and A. Mamun, *Introduction to dusty plasma physics*. CRC Press, 2001.
- [69] W. Zhu, P. Niraula, P. Almeida, M. Benilov, and D. Santos, "Self-organization in dc glow microdischarges in krypton: modelling and experiments," *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol*, vol. 23, no. 054012, p. 054012, 2014.
- [70] Y. Feng, C.-S. Ren, Q.-Y. Nie, and D.-Z. Wang, "Study on the self-organized pattern in an atmospheric pressure dielectric barrier discharge plasma jet," *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 38, no. 5, pp. 1061–1065, 2010.
- [71] L. Dong, B. Li, Z. Shen, and L. Liu, "Formation of spiral patterns in dielectric-barrier discharge investigated by an intensified-charge coupled device," *Physical Review E*, vol. 86, no. 5, p. 056217, 2012.
- [72] J. Schäfer, P. Vašina, J. Hnilica, R. Foest, V. Kudrle, and K.-D. Weltmann, "Visualization of revolving modes in rf and mw nonthermal atmospheric pressure plasma jets," *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 39, no. 11, pp. 2350–2351, 2011.
- [73] F. Iza and J. Hopwood, "Self-organized filaments, striations and other nonuniformities in nonthermal atmospheric microwave excited microdischarges," *IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 306–307, 2005.
- [74] H. Purwins and L. Stollenwerk, "Synergetic aspects of gas-discharge: lateral patterns in dc systems with a high ohmic barrier," *Plasma Physics and Controlled Fusion*, vol. 56, no. 12, p. 123001, 2014.
- [75] M. Klíma, L. Zajíčková, and J. Janča, "The perspectives of plasmachemical treatment on ancient artifacts," *Zeitschrift für schweizerische Archäologie und Kunstgeschichte*, vol. 54, no. 1, pp. 31–33, 1997.

- [76] J. Janča, M. Klíma, P. Slavíček, L. Zajíčková, *et al.*, “Hf plasma pencil - new source for plasma surface processing,” *Surface and Coatings Technology*, vol. 116, pp. 547–551, 1999.
- [77] K.-D. Weltmann, M. Polak, K. Masur, T. Von Woedtke, J. Winter, and S. Reuter, “Plasma processes and plasma sources in medicine,” *Contributions to Plasma Physics*, vol. 52, no. 7, pp. 644–654, 2012.
- [78] K.-D. Weltmann, E. Kindel, R. Brandenburg, C. Meyer, R. Bussiahn, C. Wilke, and T. Von Woedtke, “Atmospheric pressure plasma jet for medical therapy: plasma parameters and risk estimation,” *Contributions to Plasma Physics*, vol. 49, no. 9, pp. 631–640, 2009.
- [79] R. E. Sladek, E. Stoffels, R. Walraven, P. J. Tielbeek, R. Koolhoven, *et al.*, “Plasma treatment of dental cavities: a feasibility study,” *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 1540–1543, 2004.
- [80] D. Dobrynin, G. Fridman, G. Friedman, and A. Fridman, “Physical and biological mechanisms of direct plasma interaction with living tissue,” *New Journal of Physics*, vol. 11, no. 11, p. 115020, 2009.
- [81] G. Morfill, M. G. Kong, and J. Zimmermann, “Focus on plasma medicine,” *New Journal of Physics*, vol. 11, no. 11, p. 115011, 2009.
- [82] G. Fridman, G. Friedman, A. Gutsol, A. B. Shekhter, V. N. Vasilets, and A. Fridman, “Applied plasma medicine,” *Plasma Processes and Polymers*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 503–533, 2008.
- [83] M. G. Kong, G. Kroesen, G. Morfill, T. Nosenko, T. Shimizu, J. Van Dijk, and J. Zimmermann, “Plasma medicine: an introductory review,” *New Journal of Physics*, vol. 11, no. 11, p. 115012, 2009.
- [84] M. Laroussi, “Low-temperature plasmas for medicine?,” *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 37, no. 6, pp. 714–725, 2009.
- [85] E. Stoffels, A. Flikweert, W. Stoffels, and G. Kroesen, “Plasma needle: a non-destructive atmospheric plasma source for fine surface treatment of (bio) materials,” *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, vol. 11, no. 4, p. 383, 2002.
- [86] J. Schäfer, R. Foest, A. Quade, A. Ohl, and K. Weltmann, “Chemical composition of siox films deposited by an atmospheric pressure plasma jet (appj),” *Plasma Process. Polym.*, vol. 6, p. S519, 2009.
- [87] J. Schäfer, R. Foest, A. Quade, A. Ohl, M. J., and K. Weltmann, “Carbon-free siox films deposited from octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane (omcts) by an atmospheric pressure plasma jet (appj),” *Eur. Phys. J. D*, vol. 54, p. 211, 2009.
- [88] J. Benedikt, K. Focke, A. Yanguas-Gil, and A. Von Keudell, “Atmospheric pressure microplasma jet as a depositing tool,” *Applied physics letters*, vol. 89, no. 25, p. 251504, 2006.
- [89] J. Benedikt, V. Raballand, A. Yanguas-Gil, K. Focke, and A. Von Keudell, “Thin film deposition by means of atmospheric pressure microplasma jet,” *Plasma Physics and Controlled Fusion*, vol. 49, no. 12B, p. B419, 2007.

- [90] S. Babayan, J. Jeong, A. Schütze, V. Tu, M. Moravej, G. Selwyn, and R. Hicks, “Deposition of silicon dioxide films with a non-equilibrium atmospheric-pressure plasma jet,” *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, vol. 10, no. 4, p. 573, 2001.
- [91] K.-D. Weltmann and T. Von Woedtke, “Basic requirements for plasma sources in medicine,” *The European Physical Journal Applied Physics*, vol. 55, no. 01, p. 13807, 2011.
- [92] X. Lu, M. Laroussi, and V. Puech, “On atmospheric-pressure non-equilibrium plasma jets and plasma bullets,” *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, vol. 21, no. 3, p. 034005, 2012.
- [93] J. Waskoenig, K. Niemi, N. Knake, L. Graham, S. Reuter, V. Schulz-Von Der Gathen, and T. Gans, “Atomic oxygen formation in a radio-frequency driven micro-atmospheric pressure plasma jet,” *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, vol. 19, no. 4, p. 045018, 2010.
- [94] F. Iza, G. J. Kim, S. M. Lee, J. K. Lee, J. L. Walsh, Y. T. Zhang, and M. G. Kong, “Microplasmas: Sources, particle kinetics, and biomedical applications,” *Plasma Processes and Polymers*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 322–344, 2008.
- [95] U. Kogelschatz, “Filamentary, patterned, and diffuse barrier discharges,” *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 30, no. 4, pp. 1400–1408, 2002.
- [96] W. von Siemens, “Ueber die elektrostatische induction und die verzögerung des stroms in flaschendrähnen,” *Poggendorfs Ann. Phys. Chem*, vol. 102, pp. 66–122, 1857.
- [97] J. Boeuf, “Plasma display panels: physics, recent developments and key issues,” *Journal of physics D: Applied physics*, vol. 36, no. 6, p. R53, 2003.
- [98] D. Skácelová, V. Danilov, J. Schäfer, A. Quade, P. St’ahel, M. Černák, and J. Meichsner, “Room temperature plasma oxidation in dc-sbd: A new method for preparation of silicon dioxide films at atmospheric pressure,” *Materials Science and Engineering: B*, vol. 178, no. 9, pp. 651–655, 2013.
- [99] R. Foest, M. Schmidt, and K. Becker, “Microplasmas, an emerging field of low-temperature plasma science and technology,” *International Journal of Mass Spectrometry*, vol. 248, no. 3, pp. 87–102, 2006.
- [100] U. Kogelschatz, B. Eliasson, and W. Egli, “Dielectric-barrier discharges. principle and applications,” *Journal de Physique IV*, vol. 7, no. C4, pp. C4–47, 1997.
- [101] D. Skácelová, *Modification of semiconductors and oxides in plasma generated at atmospheric pressure*. PhD thesis, Masaryk university, Faculty of Science Brno, 2014.
- [102] U. Kogelschatz, “Dielectric-barrier discharges: their history, discharge physics, and industrial applications,” *Plasma chemistry and plasma processing*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 1–46, 2003.
- [103] I. Müller, E. Ammelt, and H.-G. Purwins, “Self-organized quasiparticles: Breathing filaments in a gas discharge system,” *Physical review letters*, vol. 82, no. 17, p. 3428, 1999.

- [104] L. Stollenwerk, "Interaction of current filaments in a dielectric barrier discharge system," *Plasma Physics and Controlled Fusion*, vol. 52, no. 12, p. 124017, 2010.
- [105] L. Dong, W. Fan, Y. He, and F. Liu, "Self-organized gas-discharge patterns in a dielectric-barrier discharge system," *IEEE transactions on plasma science*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 1356–1357, 2008.
- [106] N. Y. Babaeva and M. J. Kushner, "Self-organization of single filaments and diffusive plasmas during a single pulse in dielectric-barrier discharges," *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, vol. 23, no. 6, p. 065047, 2014.
- [107] J. Boeuf, B. Bernecker, T. Callegari, S. Blanco, and R. Fournier, "Generation, annihilation, dynamics and self-organized patterns of filaments in dielectric barrier discharge plasmas," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 100, no. 24, p. 244108, 2012.
- [108] S. Stauss, H. Muneoka, N. Ebato, F. Oshima, D. Pai, and K. Terashima, "Self-organized pattern formation in helium dielectric barrier discharge cryoplasmas," *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, vol. 22, no. 2, p. 025021, 2013.
- [109] B. Bernecker, T. Callegari, and J. Boeuf, "Evidence of a new form of self-organization in dbd plasmas: the quincunx structure," *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 44, no. 26, p. 262002, 2011.
- [110] J. Hnilica, V. Kudrle, P. Vašina, J. Schäfer, and V. Aubrecht, "Characterization of a periodic instability in filamentary surface wave discharge at atmospheric pressure in argon," *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 45, no. 5, p. 055201, 2012.
- [111] J. Schäfer, R. Foest, A. Quade, A. Ohl, and K. Weltmann, "Local deposition of SiO_x plasma polymer films by a miniaturized atmospheric pressure plasma jet (APPJ)," *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 41, no. 19, p. 194010, 2008.
- [112] J. Schäfer, R. Foest, A. Ohl, and K.-D. Weltmann, "Miniaturized non-thermal atmospheric pressure plasma jet - characterization of self-organized regimes," *Plasma Physics and Controlled Fusion*, vol. 51, no. 12, p. 124045, 2009.
- [113] P. Raizer Yu, "Gas discharge physics," 1991.
- [114] L. Potočňáková, J. Šperka, P. Souček, P. Zikán, J. Beckers, G. Kroesen, J. J. Van Loon, and V. Kudrle, "Hypergravity diagnostics and material synthesis in noble gas gliding arc plasma," in *Mezinárodní masarykova konference pro doktorandy a mladé vědecké pracovníky, Conference Proceedings*, pp. 4151–4160, MAGNANIM-ITAS, 2013.
- [115] A. Fridman, S. Nester, L. Kennedy, A. Saveliev, and O. Mutaf-Yardimci, "Gliding arc gas discharge," *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 211–231, 1999.
- [116] J. Zhu, Z. Sun, Z. Li, A. Ehn, M. Aldén, M. Salewski, F. Leipold, and Y. Kusano, "Dynamics, oh distributions and uv emission of a gliding arc at various flow-rates investigated by optical measurements," *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 47, no. 29, p. 295203, 2014.

- [117] Z. Bo, J. H. Yan, X. D. Li, Y. Chi, B. Chéron, and K. F. Cen, “The dependence of gliding arc gas discharge characteristics on reactor geometrical configuration,” *Plasma Chemistry and Plasma Processing*, vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 691–700, 2007.
- [118] Z. Sun, J. Zhu, Z. Li, M. Aldén, F. Leipold, M. Salewski, and Y. Kusano, “Optical diagnostics of a gliding arc,” *Optics Express*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 6028–6044, 2013.
- [119] X. Tu, L. Yu, J. Yan, K. Cen, and B. Chéron, “Dynamic and spectroscopic characteristics of atmospheric gliding arc in gas-liquid two-phase flow,” *Physics of Plasmas*, vol. 16, p. 113506, 2009.
- [120] A. Das, “Arc root dynamics in high power plasma torches - evidence of chaotic behavior,” *Pramana*, vol. 55, no. 5-6, pp. 873–886, 2000.
- [121] A. Indarto, J.-W. Choi, H. Lee, and H. K. Song, “Effect of additive gases on methane conversion using gliding arc discharge,” *Energy*, vol. 31, no. 14, pp. 2986–2995, 2006.
- [122] O. Mutaf-Yardimci, A. V. Saveliev, A. A. Fridman, and L. A. Kennedy, “Thermal and nonthermal regimes of gliding arc discharge in air flow,” *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 87, no. 4, pp. 1632–1641, 2000.
- [123] A. Czernichowski, “Gliding arc. applications to engineering and environment control,” *Pure & Appl. Chemistry*, vol. 66, no. 6, pp. 1301–1310, 1994.
- [124] F. Richard, J. Cormier, S. Pellerin, and J. Chapelle, “Physical study of a gliding arc discharge,” *Journal of applied physics*, vol. 79, no. 5, pp. 2245–2250, 1996.
- [125] A. Czernichowski, H. Nassar, A. Ranaivosoloarimanana, A. Fridman, M. Šimek, K. Musiol, E. Pawelec, and L. Dittrichova, “Spectral and electrical diagnostics of gliding arc,” *Acta Physica Polonica-Series A General Physics*, vol. 89, no. 5, pp. 595–604, 1996.
- [126] R. Burlica, M. J. Kirkpatrick, and B. R. Locke, “Formation of reactive species in gliding arc discharges with liquid water,” *Journal of Electrostatics*, vol. 64, no. 1, pp. 35–43, 2006.
- [127] S. Kolev and A. Bogaerts, “A 2d model for a gliding arc discharge,” *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, vol. 24, no. 1, p. 015025, 2015.
- [128] C. S. Kalra, A. F. Gutsol, A. Fridman, *et al.*, “Gliding arc discharges as a source of intermediate plasma for methane partial oxidation,” *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 32–41, 2005.
- [129] J. Janča and A. Czernichowski, “Wool treatment in the gas flow from gliding discharge plasma at atmospheric pressure,” *Surface and Coatings Technology*, vol. 98, no. 1, pp. 1112–1115, 1998.
- [130] Y. Kusano, S. Teodoru, F. Leipold, T. Andersen, B. F. Sørensen, N. Rozlosnik, and P. Michelsen, “Gliding arc discharge – application for adhesion improvement of fibre reinforced polyester composites,” *Surface and Coatings Technology*, vol. 202, no. 22, pp. 5579–5582, 2008.

- [131] N. Balcon, N. Benard, P. Braud, A. Mizuno, G. Touchard, and E. Moreau, "Prospects of airflow control by a gliding arc in a static magnetic field," *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 41, no. 20, p. 205204, 2008.
- [132] R. Monti, *Physics of fluids in microgravity*. CRC Press, 2002.
- [133] M. Lappa, *Fluids, Materials and Microgravity:: Numerical Techniques and Insights into Physics*. Elsevier, 2004.
- [134] A. Vailati, R. Cerbino, S. Mazzoni, C. J. Takacs, D. S. Cannell, and M. Giglio, "Fractal fronts of diffusion in microgravity," *Nature communications*, vol. 2, p. 290, 2011.
- [135] H. D. Ross, *Microgravity combustion: fire in free fall*. Academic press, 2001.
- [136] H. Ahari, R. L. Bedard, C. L. Bowes, N. Coombs, O. Dag, T. Jiang, G. A. Ozin, S. Petrov, I. Sokolov, A. Verma, *et al.*, "Effect of microgravity on the crystallization of a self-assembling layered material," *Nature*, vol. 388, no. 6645, pp. 857–860, 1997.
- [137] D. C. Hofmann and S. N. Roberts, "Microgravity metal processing: from undercooled liquids to bulk metallic glasses," *npj Microgravity*, vol. 1, 2015.
- [138] R. J. White and M. Averner, "Humans in space," *Nature*, vol. 409, no. 6823, pp. 1115–1118, 2001.
- [139] D. Moore, P. Bie, and H. Oser, *Biological and medical research in space: an overview of life sciences research in microgravity*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [140] M. Dreyer, "The drop tower bremen," *Microgravity Science and Technology*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 461–461, 2010.
- [141] J. J. Van Loon, "Some history and use of the random positioning machine, rpm, in gravity related research," *Advances in Space Research*, vol. 39, no. 7, pp. 1161–1165, 2007.
- [142] A. Borst and J. J. Van Loon, "Technology and developments for the random positioning machine, rpm," *Microgravity science and technology*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 287–292, 2009.
- [143] V. Pletser, "Short duration microgravity experiments in physical and life sciences during parabolic flights: the first 30 esa campaigns," *Acta Astronautica*, vol. 55, no. 10, pp. 829–854, 2004.
- [144] M. Krause and J. Blum, "Growth and form of planetary seedlings: results from a sounding rocket microgravity aggregation experiment," *Physical review letters*, vol. 93, no. 2, p. 021103, 2004.
- [145] H. Thomas, G. Morfill, V. Fortov, A. Ivlev, V. Molotkov, A. Lipaev, T. Hagl, H. Rothermel, S. Khrapak, R. Suetterlin, *et al.*, "Complex plasma laboratory pk-3 plus on the international space station," *New journal of physics*, vol. 10, no. 3, p. 033036, 2008.
- [146] K. Balmain, "Arc propagation, emission and damage on spacecraft dielectrics: a review," *Journal of electrostatics*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 95–108, 1987.

- [147] H. Huang, W. Pan, and C. Wu, "Arcjet thruster operated with different propellants," *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 39, no. 11, pp. 2934–2935, 2011.
- [148] M. Baeva, R. Kozakov, S. Gorchakov, and D. Uhrlandt, "Two-temperature chemically non-equilibrium modelling of transferred arcs," *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, vol. 21, no. 5, p. 055027, 2012.
- [149] M. Steenbeck, "Untersuchungen am luftlichtbogen im schwerefreien raum," *Z. tech. Physik*, vol. 18, p. 593, 1937.
- [150] C. Kenty, "Note on the behavior of high intensity mercury arcs falling freely under gravity," *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 10, no. 10, pp. 714–714, 1939.
- [151] C. Suits and H. Poritsky, "Application of heat transfer data to arc characteristics," *Physical Review*, vol. 55, no. 12, p. 1184, 1939.
- [152] B. Stocker and G. Weston, "The effect of acceleration on a filamentary discharge in inert gases," *Journal of Scientific Instruments*, vol. 43, no. 12, p. 913, 1966.
- [153] W. Stoffels, A. Flikweert, T. Nimalasuriya, J. Van der Mullen, G. Kroesen, and M. Haverlag, "Metal halide lamps: gravitational influence on color separation," *Pure and applied chemistry*, vol. 78, no. 6, pp. 1239–1252, 2006.
- [154] A. Flikweert, A. Meunier, T. Nimalasuriya, G. Kroesen, and W. Stoffels, "Imaging laser absorption spectroscopy of the metal-halide lamp under hyper-gravity conditions ranging from 1 to 10g," *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 41, no. 19, p. 195202, 2008.
- [155] A. Flikweert, T. Nimalasuriya, G. Kroesen, M. Haverlag, and W. Stoffels, "The metal-halide lamp under varying gravity conditions measured by emission and laser absorption spectroscopy," *Microgravity Science and Technology*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 319–326, 2009.
- [156] T. Nimalasuriya, A. Flikweert, M. Haverlag, P. Kemps, G. Kroesen, W. Stoffels, and J. Van der Mullen, "Metal halide lamps in the international space station iss," *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 39, no. 14, p. 2993, 2006.
- [157] T. Mieno and M. Takeguchi, "Thermal motion of carbon clusters and production of carbon nanotubes by gravity-free arc discharge," *Journal of applied physics*, vol. 99, no. 10, pp. 104301–104301, 2006.
- [158] J. Alford, G. Mason, and D. Feikema, "Free fall plasma-arc reactor for synthesis of carbon nanotubes in microgravity," *Review of scientific instruments*, vol. 77, no. 7, pp. 074101–074101, 2006.
- [159] G. Tan and T. Mieno, "Synthesis of single-walled carbon nanotubes by arc-vaporization under high gravity condition," *Thin Solid Films*, vol. 518, no. 13, pp. 3541–3545, 2010.
- [160] M. Kanai, A. Koshio, H. Shinohara, T. Mieno, A. Kasuya, Y. Ando, and X. Zhao, "High-yield synthesis of single-walled carbon nanotubes by gravity-free arc discharge," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 79, no. 18, pp. 2967–2969, 2001.

- [161] O. Kawanami, N. Sano, T. Miyamoto, A. Mineshige, T. Murakami, and H. Harima, "Effects of gravity on single-wall carbon nanotubes synthesized by arc in water," *Applied Physics A: Materials Science & Processing*, vol. 89, no. 4, pp. 929–932, 2007.
- [162] N. Sano, O. Kawanami, T. Charinpanitkul, and W. Tanthapanichakoon, "Study on reaction field in arc-in-water to produce carbon nano-materials," *Thin Solid Films*, vol. 516, no. 19, pp. 6694–6698, 2008.
- [163] Y. Abe, G. Maizza, N. Sone, Y. Nagasaka, and T. Suzuki, "A high gravity chemical vapor deposition apparatus," *Review of scientific instruments*, vol. 68, no. 11, pp. 4225–4231, 1997.
- [164] Y. Abe, G. Maizza, S. Bellingeri, M. Ishizuka, Y. Nagasaka, and T. Suzuki, "Diamond synthesis by high-gravity dc plasma cvd (hgcvd) with active control of the substrate temperature," *Acta Astronautica*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 121–127, 2001.
- [165] M. Ishikawa, S. Kamei, Y. Sato, N. Fujimori, N. Koshikawa, K. Murakami, and T. Suzuki, "A diagnostic study of plasma cvd under microgravity and its application to diamond deposition," *Advances in Space Research*, vol. 24, no. 10, pp. 1219–1223, 1999.
- [166] U. De Angelis, "The physics of dusty plasmas," *Physica Scripta*, vol. 45, no. 5, p. 465, 2006.
- [167] I. Mann, "Interplanetary medium—a dusty plasma," *Advances in Space Research*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 160–167, 2008.
- [168] L. Biennier, R. Georges, V. Chandrasekaran, B. Rowe, T. Bataille, V. Jayaram, K. Reddy, and E. Arunan, "Characterization of circumstellar carbonaceous dust analogues produced by pyrolysis of acetylene in a porous graphite reactor," *Carbon*, vol. 47, no. 14, pp. 3295–3305, 2009.
- [169] G. Alcouffe, M. Cavarroc, G. Cernogora, F. Ouni, A. Jolly, L. Boufendi, and C. Szopa, "Capacitively coupled plasma used to simulate titan's atmospheric chemistry," *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, vol. 19, no. 1, p. 015008, 2009.
- [170] J. Berndt, E. Kovačević, I. Stefanović, O. Stepanović, S. H. Hong, L. Boufendi, and J. Winter, "Some aspects of reactive complex plasmas," *Contributions to Plasma Physics*, vol. 49, no. 3, pp. 107–133, 2009.
- [171] T. Mieno, "Characteristics of the gravity-free gas-arc discharge and its application to fullerene production," *Plasma physics and controlled fusion*, vol. 46, no. 1, p. 211, 2003.
- [172] Y. Watanabe, M. Shiratani, and K. Koga, "Nucleation and subsequent growth of clusters in reactive plasmas," *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, vol. 11, no. 3A, p. A229, 2002.
- [173] J. Beckers, W. Stoffels, and G. Kroesen, "Temperature dependence of nucleation and growth of nanoparticles in low pressure ar/ch₄ rf discharges," *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 42, no. 15, p. 155206, 2009.

- [174] K. Takahashi, Y. Hayashi, and S. Adachi, "Measurement of electron density in complex plasmas of the pk-3 plus apparatus on the international space station," *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 110, no. 1, pp. 013307–013307, 2011.
- [175] C. Du, K. Sütterlin, K. Jiang, C. Räch, A. Ivlev, S. Khrapak, M. Schwabe, H. Thomas, V. Fortov, A. Lipaev, *et al.*, "Experimental investigation on lane formation in complex plasmas under microgravity conditions," *New Journal of Physics*, vol. 14, no. 7, p. 073058, 2012.
- [176] J. Beckers, T. Ockenga, M. Wolter, W. Stoffels, J. van Dijk, H. Kersten, and G. Kroesen, "Microparticles in a collisional rf plasma sheath under hypergravity conditions as probes for the electric field strength and the particle charge," *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 106, no. 11, p. 115002, 2011.
- [177] J. Schäfer, R. Foest, A. Quade, A. Ohl, and K.-D. Weltmann, "Chemical composition of siox films deposited by an atmospheric pressure plasma jet (appj)," *Plasma Processes and Polymers*, vol. 6, no. S1, pp. S519–S524, 2009.
- [178] J. Šperka, J. Schäfer, J. Hnilica, V. Kudrle, G. Gött, and R. Foest, "Non-thermal atmospheric pressure plasma jet operated in krypton and argon: Visual characterisation of discharge using high-speed camera," 2014. Poster presented at The XXII Europhysics Conference on Atomic and Molecular Physics of Ionized Gases, July 15–19, Greifswald, Germany.
- [179] S. Aldrich, "Sigma - aldrich specification sheet." <http://www.sigmaaldrich.com/>, 2015. [Online; accessed 20-August-2015].
- [180] C. A. R. Board, "Tetrakis(trimethylsiloxy)silane." http://www.arb.ca.gov/db/solvents/solvent_pages/Miscellaneous-HTML/tetrakistrimethylsiloxy.htm, 2015. [Online; accessed 20-August-2015].
- [181] D. Nečas, V. Čudek, J. Vodák, M. Ohlidal, P. Klapetek, J. Benedikt, K. Rügner, and L. Zajíčková, "Mapping of properties of thin plasma jet films using imaging spectroscopic reflectometry," *Measurement Science and Technology*, vol. 25, no. 11, p. 115201, 2014.
- [182] D. Franta, D. Nečas, and L. Zajíčková, "Models of dielectric response in disordered solids," *Optics express*, vol. 15, no. 24, pp. 16230–16244, 2007.
- [183] A. M. Turing, "The chemical basis of morphogenesis," *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London B: Biological Sciences*, vol. 237, no. 641, pp. 37–72, 1952.
- [184] J. Benedikt, S. Hofmann, N. Knake, H. Böttner, R. Reuter, A. von Keudell, and V. Schulz-von der Gathen, "Phase resolved optical emission spectroscopy of coaxial microplasma jet operated with he and ar," *The European Physical Journal D*, vol. 60, no. 3, pp. 539–546, 2010.
- [185] N. Connor and S. Daniels, "Passive acoustic diagnostics of an atmospheric pressure linear field jet including analysis in the time-frequency domain," *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 110, no. 1, p. 013308, 2011.
- [186] N. N. Greenwood and A. Earnshaw, *Chemistry of the Elements*. Elsevier, 2012.

- [187] V. Kaufman and L. Minnhagen, "Accurate ground-term combinations in ne i," *J. Opt. Soc. Am.*, vol. 62, pp. 92–95, Jan 1972.
- [188] E. Saloman and C. J. Sansonetti, "Wavelengths, energy level classifications, and energy levels for the spectrum of neutral neon," *Journal of physical and chemical reference data*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 1113–1158, 2004.
- [189] I. Velchev, W. Hogervorst, and W. Ubachs, "Precision vuv spectroscopy of ar i at 105 nm," *Journal of Physics B: Atomic, Molecular and Optical Physics*, vol. 32, no. 17, p. L511, 1999.
- [190] E. Saloman, "Energy levels and observed spectral lines of krypton, Kr I through Kr XXXVI," *Journal of physical and chemical reference data*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 215–386, 2007.
- [191] D. J. Jin, H. S. Uhm, and G. Cho, "Influence of the gas-flow reynolds number on a plasma column in a glass tube," *Physics of Plasmas (1994-present)*, vol. 20, no. 8, p. 083513, 2013.
- [192] A. liquide, "Gas encyclopedia." <http://encyclopedia.airliquide.com/>, 2015. [Online; accessed 1-August-2015].
- [193] J. Voráč, A. Obrušník, V. Procházka, P. Dvořák, and M. Talába, "Spatially resolved measurement of hydroxyl radical (oh) concentration in an argon rf plasma jet by planar laser-induced fluorescence," *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, vol. 23, no. 2, p. 025011, 2014.
- [194] O. Motret, C. Hibert, S. Pellerin, and J. Pouvesle, "Rotational temperature measurements in atmospheric pulsed dielectric barrier discharge-gas temperature and molecular fraction effects," *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 33, no. 12, p. 1493, 2000.
- [195] J. L. Walsh, F. Iza, N. B. Janson, V. Law, and M. G. Kong, "Three distinct modes in a cold atmospheric pressure plasma jet," *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 43, no. 7, p. 075201, 2010.
- [196] A. Brockhaus, R. Sauerbier, and J. Engemann, "Comparison of three excitation schemes for cylindrical dielectric barrier discharges," *The European Physical Journal Applied Physics*, vol. 47, no. 02, p. 22809, 2009.
- [197] F. Sigeneger and D. Loffhagen, "Modeling of striated filaments occurring in a non-thermal rf plasma jet at atmospheric pressure," *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 42, no. 10, pp. 2498–2499, 2014.
- [198] V. Donnelly, "Plasma electron temperatures and electron energy distributions measured by trace rare gases optical emission spectroscopy," *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 37, no. 19, p. R217, 2004.
- [199] D. A. Zayarnyi, I. Kholin, and A. Y. Chugunov, "Deactivation of 3s levels of the neon atom by collisions with neon, argon, krypton, and xenon," *Quantum Electronics*, vol. 25, no. 3, p. 217, 1995.

- [200] G. Hagelaar and L. Pitchford, “Solving the boltzmann equation to obtain electron transport coefficients and rate coefficients for fluid models,” *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, vol. 14, no. 4, p. 722, 2005.
- [201] L. Alves, K. Bartschat, S. Biagi, M. Bordage, L. Pitchford, C. Ferreira, G. Hagelaar, W. Morgan, S. Pancheshnyi, A. Phelps, *et al.*, “Comparisons of sets of electron–neutral scattering cross sections and swarm parameters in noble gases: II. helium and neon,” *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 46, no. 33, p. 334002, 2013.
- [202] L. Pitchford, L. Alves, K. Bartschat, S. Biagi, M. Bordage, A. Phelps, C. Ferreira, G. Hagelaar, W. Morgan, S. Pancheshnyi, *et al.*, “Comparisons of sets of electron–neutral scattering cross sections and swarm parameters in noble gases: I. argon,” *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 46, no. 33, p. 334001, 2013.
- [203] E. Castanos-Martinez, M. Moisan, and Y. Kabouzi, “Achieving non-contracted and non-filamentary rare-gas tubular discharges at atmospheric pressure,” *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 42, no. 1, p. 012003, 2009.
- [204] L. Dosoudilová, J. Šperka, J. Schäfer, J. Harhausen, S. Peters, Z. Navrátil, and R. Foest, “Optical emission spectroscopy of rf plasma jet in neon/argon penning mixture at atmospheric pressure,” 2014. Poster presented at The XXII Europhysics Conference on Atomic and Molecular Physics of Ionized Gases, July 15–19, Greifswald, Germany.
- [205] J. Hnilica, J. Schäfer, R. Foest, L. Zajíčková, and V. Kudrle, “Pecvd of nanostructured sio2 in a modulated microwave plasma jet at atmospheric pressure,” *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 46, no. 33, p. 335202, 2013.
- [206] Y. Akishev, M. Grushin, V. Karalnik, I. Kochetov, A. Napartovich, and N. Trushkin, “Generation of atmospheric pressure non-thermal plasma by diffusive and constricted discharges in air and nitrogen at the rest and flow,” in *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 257, p. 012014, IOP Publishing, 2010.
- [207] C. Martinet and R. Devine, “Analysis of the vibrational mode spectra of amorphous sio2 films,” *Journal of applied physics*, vol. 77, no. 9, pp. 4343–4348, 1995.
- [208] D. Anderson, *Infrared, Raman, and ultraviolet spectroscopy*, vol. 1. John Wiley & Sons: New York, 1974.
- [209] C. Rau and W. Kulisch, “Mechanisms of plasma polymerization of various silico-organic monomers,” *Thin solid films*, vol. 249, no. 1, pp. 28–37, 1994.
- [210] J. van Loon, J. Krause, H. Cunha, J. Goncalves, H. Almeida, and P. Schiller, “The large diameter centrifuge for life and physical sciences and technology,” *Proc. Of the Life in Space for Life on Earth Symposium (Angers, France 22-27 June 2008)*, vol. ESA SP-663, 2008.
- [211] ESA, “The Large diameter centrifuge.” http://www.esa.int/Education/The_Large_Diameter_Centrifuge, 2015. [Online; accessed 14-September-2015].
- [212] ESA, “LDC Experimenter Users Manual.” <http://esamultimedia.esa.int/docs/edu/LDCExperimenterUserManual-v2r2.pdf>, 2015. [Online; accessed 14-September-2015].

- [213] G. Cocconi and P. Morrison, "Searching for inter stellar communications," *Nature*, vol. 184, no. 4690, 1959.
- [214] I. Kuznetsova, N. Kalashnikov, A. Gutsol, A. Fridman, and L. Kennedy, "Effect of overshooting in the transitional regimes of the low-current gliding arc discharge," *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 92, no. 8, pp. 4231–4237, 2002.
- [215] Y. G. Utkin, S. Keshav, J.-H. Kim, J. Kastner, I. V. Adamovich, and M. Samimy, "Development and use of localized arc filament plasma actuators for high-speed flow control," *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 40, no. 3, p. 685, 2007.
- [216] A. Fridman, A. Gutsol, S. Gangoli, Y. Ju, and T. Ombrello, "Characteristics of gliding arc and its application in combustion enhancement," *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 1216–1228, 2008.
- [217] Y. Korolev, O. Frants, N. Landl, A. Bolotov, and V. Nekhoroshev, "Features of a near-cathode region in a gliding arc discharge in air flow," *Plasma Sources Science and Technology*, vol. 23, no. 5, p. 054016, 2014.
- [218] Y. D. Korolev, O. B. Frants, V. G. Geyman, N. V. Landl, and V. S. Kasyanov, "Low-current gliding arc in an air flow," *Plasma Science, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 39, no. 12, pp. 3319–3325, 2011.
- [219] D. B. Ingham and I. Pop, *Convective heat transfer: mathematical and computational modelling of viscous fluids and porous media*. Elsevier: Access Online via Elsevier, 2001.
- [220] S. Pellerin, F. Richard, J. Chapelle, J. Cormier, and K. Musiol, "Heat string model of bi-dimensional dc glidarc," *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 33, no. 19, p. 2407, 2000.
- [221] R. Finn, "Determination of the drag on a cylinder at low reynolds numbers," *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 771–773, 1953.
- [222] M. Bogaczyk, R. Wild, L. Stollenwerk, and H. Wagner, "Surface charge accumulation and discharge development in diffuse and filamentary barrier discharges operating in he, n₂ and mixtures," *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 45, no. 46, p. 465202, 2012.
- [223] A. Ferrari and J. Robertson, "Interpretation of raman spectra of disordered and amorphous carbon," *Physical Review B*, vol. 61, no. 20, p. 14095, 2000.
- [224] R. Meulenbroeks, D. Schram, M. Van De Sanden, and J. Van Der Mullen, "Wall association and recirculation in expanding thermal arc plasmas," *Physical review letters*, vol. 76, no. 11, pp. 1840–1843, 1996.